

Performance Analysis of Active RIS-Assisted Downlink NOMA With Transmit Antenna Selection

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Abstract—Active reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RISs) overcome the severe multiplicative fading effect observed in conventional passive RIS-assisted systems by amplifying the reflected signal. This paper investigates the performance of an active RIS-assisted downlink non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA) network with transceiver hardware impairments and imperfect successive interference cancellation (ipSIC). By employing the transmit antenna selection technique at the base station, closed-form expressions of the outage probability (OP) and ergodic capacity are derived in terms of the Meijer-G function. Regarding the former, we formulate the asymptotic OP and asymptotic ergodic capacity and obtain the diversity order of the system. Additionally, we explore higher-order modulation schemes such as rectangular quadrature amplitude modulation (QAM), cross QAM, and hexagonal QAM, which are integral for achieving increased data rates while maintaining power and bandwidth efficiency. For these modulation schemes, we derive closed-form expressions of the average symbol error rate (ASER) and asymptotic ASER using the Gaussian Chebyshev quadrature approximation. The performance of the considered NOMA network is compared with an orthogonal multiple access technique. In addition, the system performance is compared to that with a passive RIS. We show that the diversity order of the considered network scales with the number of transmit antennas, the number of REs, and fading mitigation parameters, and the hexagonal QAM outperforms several other QAM schemes. Finally, simulation results affirm the accuracy of the derived closed-form expressions.

Index Terms—Active RIS, hexagonal quadrature amplitude modulation (QAM), NOMA, rectangular QAM, cross QAM.

I. INTRODUCTION

Reconfigurable intelligent surface (RIS) is a key technology for next-generation wireless communication systems because of its ability to reconfigure the wireless propagation environment. RIS is a planar metasurface comprised of large number of reflecting elements (REs). The phase and/or amplitude of the incident signal are controlled by a RIS controller, thereby achieving a fine-grained reflect beamforming [1]. A passive RIS comprises numerous passive REs, each capable of reflecting the incident signal with an adjustable phase

shift, and experiences a multiplicative fading effect caused by the path loss in the transmitter-RIS-receiver link. This effect results from the multiplication of the path losses in both the transmitter-RIS and RIS-receiver links. To mitigate this effect, one may use an active RIS, which can amplify the reflected signal by replacing passive REs with active REs [2], [3]. The active REs incorporate active reflection-type amplifiers, such as asymmetric current mirrors and current-inverting converters. Consequently, an active RIS enhances the signal strength, thereby expanding both coverage and spectral efficiency as long as the thermal noise induced by the active REs remains reasonable.

Meanwhile, non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA) emerges as a prospective technology for advancing spectrum efficiency and user connectivity in next-generation wireless communication systems. Power-domain downlink NOMA enables concurrent communication between multiple users with varying power levels and utilizing the same frequency/time/code resources. Multiple user signals are combined by employing superposition coding at the transmitter while their separation is achieved through successive interference cancellation (SIC) at the receivers [4]. Incorporating active RIS with NOMA has the potential to boost the system performance by dynamically adjusting the wireless propagation environment. This is particularly beneficial for mobile users facing obstacles that may obstruct their connectivity. Hence, in this article, an active RIS-assisted NOMA network is considered.

In terms of modulation, the family of quadrature amplitude modulations (QAMs) is appealing due to its capacity to facilitate bandwidth-efficient high data-rate communication. It primarily comprises of constellations such as rectangular QAM, cross-QAM, and hexagonal QAM. The rectangular QAM constellations are formed by arranging the constellation points in a rectangular shape and fit well configurations with a number of symbols given by an odd power of two. It is commonly preferred in practical telecommunication systems due to its versatility, encompassing various modulation schemes such as multilevel amplitude shift keying, binary phase shift keying (PSK), quadrature PSK, orthogonal binary frequency shift keying, and square QAM as special cases [5]. However, the rectangular QAM is not an ideal choice due to its high average power demand. Instead, cross QAM is preferred, as it exhibits significantly lower peak and average powers compared to rectangular QAM [6]. The cross QAM constellations are formed by removing the outer corner points of the rectangular QAM and arranging them in a cross shape. It finds application in

This work is partially supported by the Finnish Foundation for Technology Promotion, Research Council of Finland (former Academy of Finland, Grant 346208 (6G Flagship Programme)). This research work is also supported by the Robust 6G project of Finnish Research Council of Finland (Grant 346208 (6G Flagship Programme)) and by the Indian Finnish Consortia for Research and Education (INDIFICORE Menot) (Grant 24650101111). (*Corresponding Author: Deepak Kumar*)

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diverse communication systems including asymmetric digital subscribers line (ADSL), very high speed digital subscribers line (VDSL), and digital video broadcasting-cable (DVB-C) [7]. Meanwhile, the pursuit of higher data rates drives research towards more condensed 2-D constellations, giving rise to the creation of a hexagonal lattice-based constellation known as hexagonal QAM. Hexagonal QAM achieves the most compact 2-D arrangement for a specified Euclidean distance among its constellation points. Consequently, it exhibits lower peak and average powers, offering optimal average symbol error rate (ASER) performance compared to other QAM constellations [8], [9]. Due to its superiority over other constellations, it has numerous applications including physical-layer network coding, multiple-antenna systems, multicarrier systems, optical communications, and advanced channel coding. Hexagonal QAM is divided into irregular and regular constellations. Nevertheless, in this paper, we exclusively focus on irregular hexagonal QAM constellations due to their optimal performance [10].

A. Related Works

Passive RIS-assisted NOMA networks are studied in [11]–[27]. In [11], a RIS-assisted downlink NOMA network is presented where the RIS is deployed closer to the cell-edge user with the premise that there is no direct link between the base station (BS) and the cell-edge user. In [12], the impact of phase shift on the performance of a RIS-assisted NOMA network is studied under both coherent and discrete phase shift designs. In [13], a new channel statistic to characterize transmitter-RIS-receiver effective gain for a RIS-assisted NOMA network is studied. In [14], performance of RIS-assisted NOMA and orthogonal multiple access (OMA) networks over Nakagami- m fading channels under both downlink and uplink transmissions is investigated. In [15], the performance of a RIS-assisted short-packet NOMA network under both perfect and imperfect SIC is studied over Rayleigh fading channels. In [16], the impact of phase shift error, transceiver hardware impairments, and imperfect SIC (ipSIC) on the performance of a RIS-assisted downlink NOMA network is studied. In [17], a deep learning framework is proposed to predict the ergodic capacity of a RIS-assisted cognitive NOMA network. In [18], a novel transmission framework for a RIS and decode-and-forward relay-assisted NOMA network is proposed. In [19], a RIS-assisted cooperative NOMA network is presented, wherein a near user (NU) works as a relay node and performs device-to-device communication with a far user (FU). In [20], the performance of a passive RIS-aided NOMA network in presence of multiple users is studied and closed-form expressions of outage probability (OP) and ergodic rate under Rayleigh fading channels are derived. In [21], passive RIS-assisted code and power-domain NOMA networks are considered, while closed-form expressions of OP and ergodic rate are derived. In [22], the outage performance of a passive RIS-aided NOMA network under Rayleigh fading channels in the absence of a direct link is investigated. In [23], a RIS-assisted cooperative NOMA mobile edge computing network is considered. In [24], [25], the adverse effects of hardware impairments (caused due to in-phase/quadrature-phase (I/Q) imbalances, phase noise,

and high power amplifier nonlinearities) on the performance of a RIS-assisted NOMA network are studied. In [26], an average symbol error probability of a RIS-assisted NOMA network is investigated for a pulse amplitude modulation and QAM schemes. In [27], the error rate performance of a RIS-assisted NOMA network with ipSIC is explored. Meanwhile, the ASER analysis of a passive RIS-assisted full-duplex two-way relay network over Rayleigh fading channels for rectangular QAM, cross QAM, and hexagonal QAM schemes is studied in [28].

As mentioned earlier, passive RIS-assisted networks suffer from the multiplicative fading effect. To address this issue, [29] proposes the use of an active RIS that amplifies the reflected signal to enhance the energy and spectrum efficiency. In [30], the joint control of an assisting active RIS phase shift and amplification matrices is investigated for a multi-user downlink NOMA network. In [31], the physical-layer security of an active RIS-assisted NOMA network with discrete RIS phase shift is presented to defend eavesdroppers. Meanwhile, the physical-layer security of an active RIS-assisted uplink single-output multiple-input NOMA network is examined in [32]. In [33], the performance of an active RIS-assisted NOMA network with hardware and SIC imperfections is studied. Therein, closed-form expressions of OP and ergodic rate are derived. In [34], an active simultaneously transmitting and reflecting surface assisted NOMA network with perfect/imperfect SIC is explored.

B. Motivation and Contributions

The research conducted in [11]–[27] has established a robust foundation for the optimization and performance analysis of passive RIS-assisted NOMA networks, while only [30]–[34] have focused on active RIS-assisted NOMA networks. Moreover, [31], [32] investigated physical layer security and [33], [34] studied performance in terms of OP and ergodic capacity, while the performance of active RIS-assisted downlink NOMA networks in terms of ASER for the higher-order modulation schemes such as rectangular QAM, cross QAM, and hexagonal QAM remain unexplored. This is precisely addressed in our current, where we consider a downlink NOMA network over Nakagami- m fading channels, where the NU (cell-center user) has direct communication with the BS, while the FU (cell-edge user) cannot establish direct communication with the BS and requires assistance from an active RIS. Moreover, note that the majority of the passive RIS [11]–[14], [16], [17], [19]–[22], [31] and the active RIS [33], [34] assisted NOMA networks studies have assessed only OP and ergodic capacity performance. In [35], [36], a bit error rate analysis is studied for a NOMA network under M -ary phase-shift keying modulation scheme. Nevertheless, higher-order QAM schemes hold substantial significance in both current and future wireless communication systems. Assessing the system's performance in these schemes requires considering ASER as a crucial performance metric. The bit error rate analysis studied for NOMA network in [35], [36] does not include consideration of RIS and higher-order QAM schemes. Meanwhile, [26], [27] have delved into the error rate analysis for a passive RIS-assisted NOMA network. To the best of the authors'

knowledge, existing active RIS-assisted NOMA related papers have not addressed ASER performance, which is critical for downlink scenarios. Additionally, [12]–[22], [24], [26]–[28], [31], [33], [34] have considered single transmit antenna at the BS; however this paper consider multiple transmit antennas and employ a transmit antenna selection (TAS) technique that provide transmit diversity gain with reduced implementation complexity [37]. Furthermore, this paper accounts for transceiver hardware and ipSIC imperfections, reflecting a practical setup. This paper addresses this gap with the following primary contributions:

- We derive the OP closed-form expression in terms of the Meijer-G function by employing a TAS technique at the BS for both the NU and the FU. These formulations encompass the influence of the number of REs, the number of antennas at the BS, hardware impairments, ipSIC, amplification gain, thermal noise introduced by the active REs, fading mitigation parameter, and various other system parameters. Furthermore, we derive a closed-form expression for the asymptotic OP at a high signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) for both the NU and FU. This facilitates determination of the diversity order for the considered network. We illustrate that the diversity order improves with the number of antennas at the BS, the number of REs, and the fading mitigation parameter due to transmit diversity gain, fine-grained reflect beamforming, and better channel condition for signal transmission, respectively.
- We derive a closed-form expression for the ergodic capacity and asymptotic ergodic capacity in terms of the Meijer-G function for both the NU and the FU by utilizing the Gaussian Chebyshev quadrature (GCQ) approximation method. The impact of the fading mitigation parameter, the number of REs, the number of transmit antennas at the BS, hardware impairments, ipSIC, amplification gain, and thermal noise are captured therein.
- We derive the ASER and asymptotic ASER closed-form expressions for both the NU and FU considering generalized rectangular QAM, cross QAM, and hexagonal QAM schemes by employing the GCQ approximation method. The expressions capture the impact of constellation size, the number of REs, the number of transmit antennas at the BS, amplification gain, thermal noise, and other system parameters. Moreover, a comparison of ASER performance is showcased for the same QAM schemes, emphasizing the superior performance of hexagonal QAM.
- Finally, we conduct Monte-Carlo simulations to validate accuracy of the derived closed-form expressions, and useful insights are drawn. Performance of the considered NOMA network is compared with that of an OMA network. Additionally, the system performance to that with a passive RIS, illustrating advantage of the active RIS implementation. We show that increasing the number of REs and amplification gain, the number of transmit antennas at the BS, and enhancing fading statistics lead to improved performance. However, there is a noticeable performance degradation with hardware impairments, ipSIC, and as the active REs' thermal noise power increases.

Fig. 1: Active RIS-assisted NOMA network.

C. Organization and Notations

Subsequent sections of the paper are structured as follows. Section II presents the system and signal model for both the NU and the FU. Sections III and IV focus on deriving performance metrics (OP, asymptotic OP, ergodic capacity, asymptotic ergodic capacity, ASER, and asymptotic ASER) for both the NU and FU, respectively. Section V and Section VI showcase results and concluding remarks, respectively.

Notations: In this paper, scalars are represented by italic letters, while vectors are denoted by boldface letters. $\Upsilon(\cdot, \cdot)$ and $\Gamma(\cdot)$ represent the lower incomplete and complete gamma functions, respectively. $\mathbb{E}\{\cdot\}$, $\mathbb{C}^{i \times j}$, and $\Pr[\cdot]$ denote statistical expectation, a complex-valued matrix of size $i \times j$, and probability, respectively. $F_W(\cdot)$ and $f_W(\cdot)$ represent the cumulative distribution function (CDF) and probability density function (PDF) of a random variable (RV) W , respectively. The term $Q(\cdot)$ represents the Gaussian-Q function, $\text{erf}(\cdot)$ represents the error function, \mathbf{I}_R represents an $R \times R$ identity matrix, ${}_1F_1(\cdot; \cdot; \cdot)$ represents a confluent hypergeometric function of first kind, and $G_{p,q}^{m,n} \left[x \left| \begin{matrix} a_1, \dots, a_n, a_{n+1}, \dots, a_p \\ b_1, \dots, b_m, b_{m+1}, \dots, b_q \end{matrix} \right. \right]$ represents the Meijer-G function [38, eq. (9.30)]. The confluent hypergeometric function is represented by ${}_1F_1(a; b; x) = \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a)_t}{(b)_t t!} x^t$, where $(\cdot)_t$ denotes the Pochhammer symbol and “!” denotes the factorial [38, eq. (9.14.1)].

II. SYSTEM MODEL

As illustrated in Fig. 1, we consider an active RIS-assisted downlink NOMA network consisting of a BS (s), active RIS, NU (n), and FU (f). Specifically, the NU is a cell-center user having a direct link with the BS, whereas the FU is a cell-edge user facing shadowing effect and devoid of a direct link with the BS. Consequently, the FU needs assistance from the active RIS for communication. The BS is equipped with N_s transmit antennas, and NU and FU are equipped with a single antenna. The active RIS is composed of R REs, with each RE being equipped with a specialized active reflection-type amplifier, such as an asymmetric current mirror, current-inverting converters, or certain integrated circuits, and a phase-shift circuit. The R active REs possess the capability to amplify the incoming signal, thereby mitigating the impact of multiplicative fading bottlenecks. The reflection-coefficient matrix of the considered active RIS is denoted by $\Theta = \text{diag}(\alpha_1 e^{j\theta_1}, \dots, \alpha_R e^{j\theta_R})$, where $\alpha_r > 1$ is the amplification gain and $\theta_r \in [0, 2\pi)$ is the phase-shift of the r^{th} RE with $r = 1, 2, \dots, R$. The channel fading coefficients between the BS and the NU, the BS and the r^{th} RE of the active RIS,

and the r^{th} RE of the active RIS and the FU are denoted by $\mathbf{h}_{\text{sn}} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_s \times 1}$, $\mathbf{h}_{\text{sr}} \in \mathbb{C}^{1 \times R}$, and $\mathbf{h}_{\text{rf}} \in \mathbb{C}^{R \times 1}$, respectively. We consider that all channels exhibit quasi-static behavior, and perfect channel state information (CSI) is available at the BS [11], [12], [14], while the degrading impact of imperfect CSI is left for future work. The channel coefficients undergo Nakagami- m fading, where m denotes the fading mitigation parameter. Specifically, fading mitigation of the BS-NU, BS- r^{th} RE of the active RIS, and r^{th} RE of the active RIS-FU links are denoted as m_{sn} , m_{sr} , and m_{rf} , respectively. Furthermore, the average power of the BS-NU, BS- r^{th} RE of the active RIS, and r^{th} RE of the active RIS-FU links are denoted as Ω_{sn} , Ω_{sr} , and Ω_{rf} , respectively.

A. Signal Model

The BS transmits superimposed information signals to both the NU and FU through power domain multiplexing and superposition coding [4], [12]. The transmitted signal can be written as $x_s = \sqrt{\beta_n}x_n + \sqrt{\beta_f}x_f$, where x_n and x_f denote the transmitted signals to the NU and the FU, respectively. The terms β_n and β_f denote the power allocation coefficients for the NU and FU, respectively, and $\beta_n + \beta_f = 1$. Please note that we have considered a fixed power allocation shared between the NU and FU, and set $\beta_n < \beta_f$ [11], [12], while the performance under various power allocation schemes would be an interesting direction for future work.

The BS selects an antenna j ($1 \leq j \leq N_s$) among N_s transmit antennas by employing a TAS technique to broadcast information to NU and FU with the aim of finding the best channel condition for the BS \rightarrow NU and BS \rightarrow FU links, as proposed in [39]. The received signals at the NU and the FU in the presence of transceiver hardware impairments are given respectively by

$$y_n = \sqrt{P_s}h_{s,j,n}(x_s + \eta_s) + \eta_n + w_n, \quad (1)$$

$$y_f = \sqrt{P_s}h_{s,j,r}\Theta\mathbf{h}_{\text{rf}}(x_s + \eta_s) + \mathbf{h}_{\text{rf}}\Theta\mathbf{w}_r + \eta_f + w_f, \quad (2)$$

where P_s denotes the transmit power at the BS. The term $w_n \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma_n^2)$, $\mathbf{w}_r \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma_r^2 \mathbf{I}_R)$, and $w_f \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma_f^2)$ denote the additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) at the NU, thermal noise introduced by the active REs, and the AWGN at the FU, respectively. The term $\eta_s \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \phi_s^2)$, $\eta_n \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \phi_n^2 P_s |h_{s,j,n}|^2)$, and $\eta_f \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \phi_f^2 P_s |h_{s,j,r}\Theta\mathbf{h}_{\text{rf}}|^2)$ denote the distortion noises due to hardware impairments at the BS, the NU, and the FU, respectively [40]–[42]. Furthermore, the term ϕ_s , ϕ_n , and ϕ_f characterize the level of impairments in the BS, the NU, and the FU, respectively.

At the NU, the signal of the FU is initially decoded, and the corresponding received instantaneous signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR) is given as

$$\Lambda_{n \rightarrow f} = \frac{\zeta_n \beta_f |h_{s,j,n}|^2}{\zeta_n (\beta_n + \phi_s^2 + \phi_n^2) |h_{s,j,n}|^2 + 1}, \quad (3)$$

where $\zeta_n = \frac{P_s}{\sigma_n^2}$. Following SIC implementation, the signal of the NU is decoded, and the corresponding received instantaneous SNR is given as

$$\Lambda_n = \frac{\zeta_n \beta_n |h_{s,j,n}|^2}{\zeta_n (\rho \beta_f + \phi_s^2 + \phi_n^2) |h_{s,j,n}|^2 + 1}, \quad (4)$$

where ρ ($0 \leq \rho \leq 1$) represents residual interference because of the ipSIC and $\rho = 0$ illustrates perfect SIC [43]. At the FU, its signal is first decoded directly, treating the NU's signal as interference, and the corresponding received instantaneous SINR is given as

$$\Lambda_f = \frac{\zeta_f \beta_f \alpha^2 |h_{s,j,r}\Phi\mathbf{h}_{\text{rf}}|^2}{\zeta_f \alpha^2 (\beta_n + \phi_s^2 + \phi_f^2) |h_{s,j,r}\Phi\mathbf{h}_{\text{rf}}|^2 + \lambda |\mathbf{h}_{\text{rf}}\Phi|^2 + 1}, \quad (5)$$

where $\zeta_f = \frac{P_s}{\sigma_f^2}$ and $\lambda = \frac{\alpha^2 \sigma_r^2}{\sigma_f^2}$. Here, for simplicity, we consider $\alpha_r = \alpha$ and define $\Theta = \alpha \Phi$, where $\Phi = \text{diag}(e^{j\theta_1}, \dots, e^{j\theta_R})$.

III. NEAR USER PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

In this section, we analyze the NU performance in terms of OP, asymptotic OP, ergodic capacity, asymptotic ergodic capacity, ASER, and asymptotic ASER.

A. Outage Probability

In a transmission system with delay limitations, OP is an important performance metric capturing the probability of link failure. The OP of the NU is given as

$$\mathbb{P}_n = 1 - \Pr[\Lambda_{n \rightarrow f} \geq \Lambda_{\text{thf}}, \Lambda_n \geq \Lambda_{\text{thn}}], \quad (6)$$

where $\Lambda_{\text{thf}} = 2^{\mathcal{R}_f} - 1$, $\Lambda_{\text{thn}} = 2^{\mathcal{R}_n} - 1$. The terms \mathcal{R}_f and \mathcal{R}_n denote the target rates of the FU and NU, respectively. Further, the diversity order of the NU communication link is evaluated from the asymptotic OP by approximating the OP at high SNR.

Theorem 1: OP and asymptotic OP are given in closed-form respectively as

$$\mathbb{P}_n = \left(1 - \sum_{p=0}^{m_{\text{sn}}-1} \frac{1}{p!} \left(\frac{m_{\text{sn}} \Xi}{\Omega_{\text{sn}} \zeta_n} \right)^p G_{0,1}^{1,0} \left[\frac{m_{\text{sn}} \Xi}{\Omega_{\text{sn}} \zeta_n} \middle| 0 \right] \right)^{N_s}, \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbb{P}_n^\infty \approx \left\{ \frac{1}{m_{\text{sn}} \Gamma(m_{\text{sn}})} \left(\frac{m_{\text{sn}} \Xi}{\Omega_{\text{sn}}} \right)^{m_{\text{sn}}} \right\}^{N_s} \zeta_n^{-m_{\text{sn}} N_s}, \quad (8)$$

where $\Xi = \max \left\{ \frac{\Lambda_{\text{thf}}}{\beta_f - (\beta_n + \phi_s^2 + \phi_n^2) \Lambda_{\text{thf}}}, \frac{\Lambda_{\text{thn}}}{\beta_n - (\rho \beta_f + \phi_s^2 + \phi_n^2) \Lambda_{\text{thn}}} \right\}$. From (7), it can be observed that the OP depends on the fading mitigation parameter m_{sn} , level of impairments ϕ_s and ϕ_n , residual interference ρ , power allocation coefficient β_n and β_f , and the number of transmit antennas N_s at the BS. Furthermore, from (8), the diversity order of the NU is $m_{\text{sn}} N_s$, the fading mitigation parameter of the BS-NU link and the number of transmit antennas at the BS.

Proof: Refer to Appendix A.

B. Ergodic Capacity

Ergodic capacity, expressed in bps/Hz, quantifies the theoretical upper limit for reliable communication in a fading channel. Ergodic capacity is computed by averaging the instantaneous capacity over fading channels. The ergodic capacity of the NU is given as [14]

$$\mathbb{C}_n = \mathbb{E} \{ \log_2(1 + \Lambda_n) \} = \int_0^\infty \log_2(1 + \gamma) f_{\Lambda_n}(\gamma) d\gamma. \quad (9)$$

The PDF $f_{\Lambda_n}(\gamma)$ is obtained by taking the derivative of the cumulative distribution function (CDF) $F_{\Lambda_n}(\gamma)$. The CDF $F_{\Lambda_n}(\gamma)$ is obtained by utilizing (4), and is given as

$$F_{\Lambda_n}(\gamma) = \sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(m_{sn}-1)} \binom{N_s}{q} (-1)^q \varphi_p^q \left(\frac{\gamma}{\beta_n - \varpi\gamma} \right)^p e^{-\frac{m_{sn}q\gamma}{\Omega_{sn}\zeta_n(\beta_n - \varpi\gamma)}}. \quad (10)$$

where $\varpi = \rho\beta_f + \phi_s^2 + \phi_n^2$. The term φ_p^q can be recursively calculated as $\varphi_0^q = (\delta_0)^q$, $\varphi_1^q = q(\delta_1)$, $\varphi_q^{q(m_{sn}-1)} = (\delta_{m_{sn}-1})^q$ for $0 \leq p \leq q(m_{sn}-1)$, $\varphi_p^q = \frac{1}{p\delta_0} \sum_{s=1}^p [(sq-p+s)\delta_s\varphi_{p-s}^q]$ for $2 \leq p \leq (m_{sn}-1)$, and $\varphi_p^q = \frac{1}{p\delta_0} \sum_{s=1}^{m_{sn}-1} [(sq-p+s)\delta_s\varphi_{p-s}^q]$ for $m_{sn} \leq p \leq q(m_{sn}-1)$, where $\delta_p = \frac{1}{p!} \left(\frac{m_{sn}}{\Omega_{sn}\zeta_n} \right)^p$ [44]. Furthermore, the PDF $f_{\Lambda_n}(\gamma)$ is obtained by differentiating the CDF $F_{\Lambda_n}(\gamma)$, and is given as

$$f_{\Lambda_n}(\gamma) = \sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(m_{sn}-1)} \binom{N_s}{q} (-1)^q \varphi_p^q e^{-\frac{m_{sn}q\gamma}{\Omega_{sn}\zeta_n(\beta_n - \varpi\gamma)}} \times \left\{ \frac{p\beta_n\gamma^{p-1}}{(\beta_n - \varpi\gamma)^{p+1}} - \frac{q\beta_n m_{sn}\gamma^p}{\Omega_{sn}\zeta_n(\beta_n - \varpi\gamma)^{p+2}} \right\}. \quad (11)$$

On invoking (11) in (9) and representing $\log_2(1+\gamma) = G_{2,2}^{1,2}[\gamma|_{1,0}^{1,1}]$ and by employing the GCQ approximation method, the ergodic capacity is given as

$$C_n \approx \sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(m_{sn}-1)} \sum_{i=1}^H \binom{N_s}{q} \Psi_i (-1)^q \varphi_p^q e^{-\frac{q m_{sn} \gamma_i}{\Omega_{sn} \zeta_n (\beta_n - \varpi \gamma_i)}} \times \left\{ \frac{p\beta_n \gamma_i^{p-1}}{(\beta_n - \varpi \gamma_i)^{p+1}} - \frac{q\beta_n m_{sn} \gamma_i^p}{\Omega_{sn} \zeta_n (\beta_n - \varpi \gamma_i)^{p+2}} \right\} G_{2,2}^{1,2}[\gamma_i|_{1,0}^{1,1}], \quad (12)$$

where $\Psi_i = 2\pi\sqrt{1-x_i^2}/(H(1-x_i^2))$, $x_i = \cos((2i-1)\pi/2H)$, $\gamma_i = (1+x_i)/(1-x_i)$, and H is a complexity-accuracy trade-off parameter [45]. From (12), it is noted that the ergodic capacity relies on the system parameters m_{sn} , ϕ_s , ϕ_n , ρ , β_n , β_f , and N_s .

The asymptotic ergodic capacity can be approximated as [45]

$$C_n^\infty \approx \mathbb{E} \{ \log_2(\Lambda_n) \} = \log_2 \left(\int_0^\infty \gamma f_{\Lambda_n}(\gamma) d\gamma \right). \quad (13)$$

On invoking (11) in (13) and by employing the GCQ approximation, the asymptotic ergodic capacity is given as

$$C_n^\infty \approx \log_2 \left(\sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(m_{sn}-1)} \sum_{i=1}^H \binom{N_s}{q} \Psi_i (-1)^q \varphi_p^q e^{-\frac{q m_{sn} \gamma_i}{\Omega_{sn} \zeta_n (\beta_n - \varpi \gamma_i)}} \times \left\{ \frac{p\beta_n \gamma_i^p}{(\beta_n - \varpi \gamma_i)^{p+1}} - \frac{q\beta_n m_{sn} \gamma_i^{p+1}}{\Omega_{sn} \zeta_n (\beta_n - \varpi \gamma_i)^{p+2}} \right\} \right). \quad (14)$$

C. Average Symbol Error Rate

The CDF-based generalized expression of the ASER for any modulation scheme is given as [8], [10]

$$\mathbb{P}_{e,n} = - \int_0^\infty \mathcal{P}'_s(e|\gamma) F_{\Lambda_n}(\gamma) d\gamma, \quad (15)$$

where $\mathcal{P}'_s(e|\gamma)$ represents the first-order derivative of the conditional symbol error probability (SEP) $\mathcal{P}_s(e|\gamma)$. Note that

the ASER closed-form expression derived here are valid for integer values of the fading mitigation parameters.

1) *Rectangular QAM*: The conditional SEP of $M_a \times N_a$ rectangular QAM over AWGN channel is expressed as [46]

$$\mathcal{P}_s^{\text{RQAM}}(e|\gamma) = 2 \left[c_1 Q(c_3\sqrt{\gamma}) (1 - 2c_2 Q(c_4\sqrt{\gamma})) + c_2 Q(c_4\sqrt{\gamma}) \right], \quad (16)$$

where M_a and N_a denote the in-phase and quadrature phase constellation points, respectively. Here, $c_1 = 1 - \frac{1}{M_a}$, $c_2 = 1 - \frac{1}{N_a}$, $c_3 = \sqrt{6/((M_a^2-1) + (N_a^2-1)\epsilon)}$, $c_4 = \epsilon c_3$, and the ratio $\epsilon = d_Q/d_I$ denotes the distance between quadrature and in-phase decision. Substituting the identity $Q(\gamma) = 1/2 [1 - \text{erf}(\gamma/\sqrt{2})]$ in (16) and by using [47, eq. (7.1.21)], the first-order derivative of the conditional SEP is given as

$$\mathcal{P}'_s^{\text{RQAM}}(e|\gamma) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\gamma}} \left[\mathbb{B}_1 e^{-\frac{c_3^2\gamma}{2}} + \mathbb{B}_2 e^{-\frac{c_4^2\gamma}{2}} \right] - \mathbb{B}_3 e^{-\frac{(c_3^2+c_4^2)\gamma}{2}} \times \left[{}_1F_1\left(1; \frac{3}{2}; \frac{c_3^2\gamma}{2}\right) + {}_1F_1\left(1; \frac{3}{2}; \frac{c_4^2\gamma}{2}\right) \right], \quad (17)$$

where $\mathbb{B}_1 = c_1(c_2-1)c_3/\sqrt{2\pi}$, $\mathbb{B}_2 = (c_1-1)c_2c_4/\sqrt{2\pi}$, and $\mathbb{B}_3 = c_1c_3c_4/\pi$. On invoking (17) and (10) in (15), and by using the GCQ approximation, a closed-form ASER expression for rectangular QAM is derived as

$$\mathbb{P}_{e,n}^{\text{RQAM}} \approx \sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(m_{sn}-1)} \sum_{i=1}^H \binom{N_s}{q} \Psi_i (-1)^q \varphi_p^q e^{-\frac{q m_{sn} \gamma_i}{\Omega_{sn} \zeta_n (\beta_n - \varpi \gamma_i)}} \times \left[-\frac{\mathbb{B}_1 \gamma_i^{p-\frac{1}{2}}}{(\beta_n - \varpi \gamma_i)^p} e^{-\frac{c_3^2}{2}\gamma_i} - \frac{\mathbb{B}_2 \gamma_i^{p-\frac{1}{2}}}{(\beta_n - \varpi \gamma_i)^p} e^{-\frac{c_4^2}{2}\gamma_i} + \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \mathbb{B}_3 \mathbb{B}_4 \frac{\gamma_i^{t+p}}{(\beta_n - \varpi \gamma_i)^p} e^{-\frac{c_3^2+c_4^2}{2}\gamma_i} \right], \quad (18)$$

where $\mathbb{B} = (1)_t / ((3/2)_t t!)$ and $\mathbb{B}_4 = (c_3^2/2)^t + (c_4^2/2)^t$.

The asymptotic ASER can be approximated from (15) by approximating the CDF $F_{\Lambda_n}(\gamma)$ (10) at high SNR which is given as

$$F_{\Lambda_n}^\infty(\gamma) \approx \mathcal{A}_n \left(\frac{\gamma}{\beta_n - \varpi\gamma} \right)^{m_{sn}N_s} \zeta_n^{-m_{sn}N_s}, \quad (19)$$

where $\mathcal{A}_n = (1/m_{sn}\Gamma(m_{sn}))^{N_s} (m_{sn}/\Omega_{sn})^{m_{sn}N_s}$. On invoking (17) and (19) in (15) and using the GCQ approximation, the asymptotic ASER for rectangular QAM is derived as

$$\mathbb{P}_{e,n}^{\text{RQAM},\infty} \approx \mathcal{A}_1 \zeta_n^{-m_{sn}N_s}, \quad (20)$$

where

$$\mathcal{A}_1 = \sum_{i=1}^H \Psi_i \mathcal{A}_n \left(\frac{\gamma_i}{\beta_n - \varpi\gamma_i} \right)^{m_{sn}N_s} \left[-\mathbb{B}_1 \gamma_i^{-\frac{1}{2}} e^{-\frac{c_3^2}{2}\gamma_i} - \mathbb{B}_2 \gamma_i^{-\frac{1}{2}} e^{-\frac{c_4^2}{2}\gamma_i} + \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \mathbb{B}_3 \mathbb{B}_4 \gamma_i^t e^{-\frac{c_3^2+c_4^2}{2}\gamma_i} \right]. \quad (21)$$

From (20), the diversity order of the NU is given as $m_{sn}N_s$, the fading mitigation parameter of the BS-NU link and the number of transmit antennas at the BS.

2) *Cross QAM*: The conditional SEP of cross QAM over the AWGN channel is expressed as [48]

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{P}_s^{\text{XQAM}}(e|\gamma) &= k_1 Q\left(\sqrt{\frac{2\gamma}{k_2}}\right) + \frac{8}{M_a N_a} \left[\sum_{u=1}^{\frac{k_3}{2}-1} Q\left(2u\sqrt{\frac{2\gamma}{k_2}}\right) \right. \\ &\quad + Q\left(k_3\sqrt{\frac{2\gamma}{g}}\right) - 2 \sum_{u=1}^{\frac{k_3}{2}-1} Q\left(\sqrt{\frac{2\gamma}{k_2}}\right) Q\left(2u\sqrt{\frac{2\gamma}{k_2}}\right) \\ &\quad \left. - Q\left(\sqrt{\frac{2\gamma}{k_2}}\right) Q\left(k_3\sqrt{\frac{2\gamma}{k_2}}\right) \right] - k_4 Q^2\left(\sqrt{\frac{2\gamma}{k_2}}\right), \quad (22) \end{aligned}$$

where $k_1 = 4 - \frac{2(M_a + N_a)}{M_a N_a}$, $k_2 = \frac{2}{3} \left(\frac{31M_a N_a}{32} - 1 \right)$, $k_3 = \frac{M_a - N_a}{2}$, and $k_4 = 4 - \frac{4(M_a + N_a)}{M_a N_a} + \frac{8}{M_a N_a}$. By substituting $Q(\gamma) = 1/2 [1 - \text{erf}(\gamma/\sqrt{2})]$ into (22) and using [47, eq. (7.1.21)], the first-order derivative of conditional SEP is obtained as (23), where $k_5 = \frac{M_a - N_a}{M_a N_a}$, $k_6 = \frac{4u^2 + 1}{k_2}$, $\mathbb{B}_5 = (-k_1 + \frac{12}{M_a N_a} + k_4)/(2\sqrt{\pi k_2})$, $\mathbb{B}_6 = k_5/\sqrt{\pi k_2}$, $\mathbb{B}_7 = 16u/(\pi k_2 M_a N_a)$, $\mathbb{B}_8 = 2k_5/\pi k_2$, and $\mathbb{B}_9 = k_4/\pi k_2$. On invoking (23) and (10) in (15), and solving by using the GCQ approximation, a closed-form expression of ASER for cross QAM is derived as (24), where $\mathbb{B}_{10} = (1/k_2)^t + (4u^2/k_2)^t$, and $\mathbb{B}_{11} = (1/k_2)^t + (k_3/k_2)^t$.

The asymptotic ASER for cross QAM is obtained by substituting (23) and (19) in (15), which is given as

$$\mathbb{P}_{e,n}^{\text{XQAM},\infty} \approx \mathcal{A}_2 \zeta_n^{-m_{\text{sn}} N_s}, \quad (25)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}_2 &= \sum_{i=1}^H \Psi_i \mathcal{A}_n \left(\frac{\gamma_i}{\beta_n - \varpi \gamma_i} \right)^{m_{\text{sn}} N_s} \left[-\mathbb{B}_5 \gamma_i^{-\frac{1}{2}} e^{-\frac{\gamma_i}{k_2}} \right. \\ &\quad + \mathbb{B}_6 \gamma_i^{-\frac{1}{2}} e^{-\frac{k_3^2}{k_2} \gamma_i} + \sum_{u=1}^{\frac{k_3}{2}-1} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \mathbb{B}_7 \mathbb{B}_{10}^t \gamma_i^t e^{-k_6 \gamma_i} + \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \mathbb{B}_8 \mathbb{B}_{11} \\ &\quad \left. \times \gamma_i^t e^{-\frac{1+k_3^2}{k_2} \gamma_i} + \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \mathbb{B}_9 \left(\frac{1}{k_2} \right)^t \gamma_i^t e^{-\frac{2}{k_2} \gamma_i} \right]. \quad (26) \end{aligned}$$

From (25), the diversity order of the NU is given as $m_{\text{sn}} N_s$, the fading mitigation parameter of the BS-NU link and the number of transmit antennas at the BS.

3) *Hexagonal QAM*: The conditional SEP of hexagonal QAM in the presence of the AWGN channel is given as [8]

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{P}_s^{\text{HQAM}}(e|\gamma) &= g_1 Q(\sqrt{g_3 \gamma}) + \frac{2}{3} g_2 Q^2\left(\sqrt{\frac{2g_3 \gamma}{3}}\right) \\ &\quad - 2g_2 Q(\sqrt{g_3 \gamma}) Q\left(\sqrt{\frac{g_3 \gamma}{3}}\right), \quad (27) \end{aligned}$$

where g_1 , g_2 , and g_3 are constants and the values for various constellations in case of irregular HQAM (optimum) is given in [10, TABLE I]. The first order derivative of (27) is given as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{P}_s^{\text{HQAM}}(e|\gamma) &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{\gamma}} \left[\mathbb{B}_{12} e^{-\frac{g_3 \gamma}{2}} - \mathbb{B}_{13} e^{-\frac{g_3 \gamma}{3}} + \mathbb{B}_{14} e^{-\frac{g_3 \gamma}{6}} \right] \\ &\quad + \mathbb{B}_{15} e^{-\frac{2g_3 \gamma}{3}} {}_1F_1\left(1; \frac{3}{2}; \frac{g_3 \gamma}{3}\right) - \mathbb{B}_{16} e^{-\frac{2g_3 \gamma}{3}} \\ &\quad \times \left[{}_1F_1\left(1; \frac{3}{2}; \frac{g_3 \gamma}{2}\right) + {}_1F_1\left(1; \frac{3}{2}; \frac{g_3 \gamma}{6}\right) \right], \quad (28) \end{aligned}$$

where $\mathbb{B}_{12} = \sqrt{g_3/2\pi}(g_2 - g_1)/2$, $\mathbb{B}_{13} = \sqrt{g_3/3\pi}g_2/3$, $\mathbb{B}_{14} = \sqrt{g_3/6\pi}g_2/2$, $\mathbb{B}_{15} = 2g_2g_3/9\pi$, and $\mathbb{B}_{16} = g_2g_3/2\sqrt{3}\pi$. On invoking (28) and (10) in (15), and by using the GCQ approximation, a closed-form expression of ASER for hexagonal QAM is derived as (29), where $\mathbb{B}_{17} = (g_3/2)^t + (g_3/6)^t$.

The asymptotic ASER for hexagonal QAM is derived by substituting (29) and (19) in (15), which is given as

$$\mathbb{P}_{e,n}^{\text{HQAM},\infty} \approx \mathcal{A}_3 \zeta_n^{-m_{\text{sn}} N_s}, \quad (30)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}_3 &= \sum_{i=1}^H \Psi_i \mathcal{A}_n \left(\frac{\gamma_i}{\beta_n - \varpi \gamma_i} \right)^{m_{\text{sn}} N_s} \left[-\mathbb{B}_{12} \gamma_i^{-\frac{1}{2}} e^{-\frac{g_3}{2} \gamma_i} \right. \\ &\quad + \mathbb{B}_{13} \gamma_i^{-\frac{1}{2}} e^{-\frac{g_3}{3} \gamma_i} - \mathbb{B}_{14} \gamma_i^{-\frac{1}{2}} e^{-\frac{g_3}{6} \gamma_i} - \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \mathbb{B}_{15} \\ &\quad \left. \times \left(\frac{g_3}{3} \right)^t \gamma_i^t e^{-\frac{2g_3}{3} \gamma_i} + \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \mathbb{B}_{16} \mathbb{B}_{17}^t \gamma_i^t e^{-\frac{2g_3}{3} \gamma_i} \right]. \quad (31) \end{aligned}$$

From (30), the diversity order of the NU is given as $m_{\text{sn}} N_s$.

IV. FAR USER PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

Similar to Section III, herein we analyze the FU performance by deriving the closed-form expressions of OP, asymptotic OP, ergodic capacity, asymptotic ergodic capacity, ASER, and asymptotic ASER.

A. Outage Probability

The outage event at the FU is declared if the received instantaneous SINR Λ_f (as given in (5)) at the FU lies under a pre-defined threshold Λ_{thf} . To facilitate mathematical analysis, Λ_f can be approximated using its lower bound (LB) and upper bound (UB), which are respectively given as

$$\Lambda_f^{\text{LB}} \approx \frac{1}{3} \min \left(\frac{\beta_f}{\vartheta}, \frac{\zeta_f \beta_f \alpha^2 |\mathbf{h}_{s,f} \Phi \mathbf{h}_{rf}|^2}{\lambda |\mathbf{h}_{rf} \Phi|^2}, \zeta_f \beta_f \alpha^2 |\mathbf{h}_{s,f} \Phi \mathbf{h}_{rf}|^2 \right), \quad (31)$$

$$\Lambda_f^{\text{UB}} \approx \min \left(\frac{\beta_f}{\vartheta}, \frac{\zeta_f \beta_f \alpha^2 |\mathbf{h}_{s,f} \Phi \mathbf{h}_{rf}|^2}{\lambda |\mathbf{h}_{rf} \Phi|^2}, \zeta_f \beta_f \alpha^2 |\mathbf{h}_{s,f} \Phi \mathbf{h}_{rf}|^2 \right), \quad (32)$$

where $\vartheta = \beta_n + \phi_s^2 + \phi_f^2$. The LB of the OP can be evaluated by comparing the UB of the received instantaneous SINR $\Lambda_{\text{act}}^{\text{UB}}$ with Λ_{thf} as given in (33), where

$$\mathcal{I}_f = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \beta_f > \vartheta \max(\Lambda_{\text{thf}}, 1), \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (34)$$

Further, the diversity order of the FU communication link is evaluated from the asymptotic OP by approximating the OP at high SNR. The second term \mathcal{I}_1 and the last term \mathcal{I}_2 in (33) and their corresponding high SNR approximations \mathcal{I}_1^∞ and \mathcal{I}_2^∞ are given in Lemma 2 and Lemma 3, respectively.

Lemma 2: The term \mathcal{I}_1 and \mathcal{I}_1^∞ are given respectively as

$$\mathcal{I}_1 = \sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \Psi_1 \Lambda_{\text{thf}}^{\frac{q\mu}{2}} \mathbf{G}_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\alpha_1 \Lambda_{\text{thf}} |0, \frac{1}{2}|^{1-\frac{p}{2}-m_{\text{tr}} R} \right], \quad (35)$$

$$\mathcal{I}_1^\infty \approx \mathcal{A}_4 \Lambda_{\text{thf}}^{\frac{\mu N_s}{2}} \zeta_f^{-\frac{\mu N_s}{2}}, \quad (36)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{P}_s^{\text{XQAM}}(e|\gamma) = & \mathbb{B}_5 \gamma^{-\frac{1}{2}} e^{-\frac{\gamma}{k_2}} - \mathbb{B}_6 \gamma^{-\frac{1}{2}} e^{-\frac{k_3 \gamma}{k_2}} - \sum_{u=1}^{\frac{k_3}{2}-1} \mathbb{B}_7 e^{-k_6 \gamma} \left\{ {}_1F_1 \left(1; \frac{3}{2}; \frac{\gamma}{k_2} \right) + {}_1F_1 \left(1; \frac{3}{2}; \frac{4u^2 \gamma}{k_2} \right) \right\} \\ & - \mathbb{B}_8 e^{-\frac{(1+k_3)\gamma}{k_2}} \left\{ {}_1F_1 \left(1; \frac{3}{2}; \frac{\gamma}{k_2} \right) + {}_1F_1 \left(1; \frac{3}{2}; \frac{k_3 \gamma}{k_2} \right) \right\} - \mathbb{B}_9 e^{-\frac{2\gamma}{k_2}} {}_1F_1 \left(1; \frac{3}{2}; \frac{\gamma}{k_2} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}_{e,n}^{\text{XQAM}} \approx & \sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(m_{\text{sn}}-1)} \sum_{i=1}^H \binom{N_s}{q} \frac{(-1)^q \varphi_p^q 2\pi \sqrt{1-x_i^2}}{H(1-x_i^2)} e^{-\frac{qm_{\text{sn}}\gamma_i}{\Omega_{\text{sn}}\zeta_n(\beta_n - \varpi\gamma_i)}} \left[-\mathbb{B}_5 \frac{\gamma_i^{p-\frac{1}{2}}}{(\beta_n - \varpi\gamma_i)^p} e^{-\frac{1}{k_2}\gamma_i} + \mathbb{B}_6 \frac{\gamma_i^{p-\frac{1}{2}}}{(\beta_n - \varpi\gamma_i)^p} e^{-\frac{k_3}{k_2}\gamma_i} \right. \\ & \left. + \sum_{u=1}^{\frac{k_3}{2}-1} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \mathbb{B}_7 \mathbb{B}_{10} \frac{\gamma_i^{t+p}}{(\beta_n - \varpi\gamma_i)^p} e^{-k_6\gamma_i} + \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \mathbb{B}_8 \mathbb{B}_{11} \frac{\gamma_i^{t+p}}{(\beta_n - \varpi\gamma_i)^p} e^{-\frac{1+k_3}{k_2}\gamma_i} + \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \mathbb{B}_9 \frac{1}{k_2} \frac{\gamma_i^{t+p}}{(\beta_n - \varpi\gamma_i)^p} e^{-\frac{2}{k_2}\gamma_i} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}_{e,n}^{\text{HQAM}} \approx & \sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(m_{\text{sn}}-1)} \sum_{i=1}^H \binom{N_s}{q} \Psi_i (-1)^q \varphi_p^q e^{-\frac{qm_{\text{sn}}\gamma_i}{\Omega_{\text{sn}}\zeta_n(\beta_n - \varpi\gamma_i)}} \left[-\frac{\mathbb{B}_{12}\gamma_i^{p-\frac{1}{2}}}{(\beta_n - \varpi\gamma_i)^p} e^{-\frac{g_3}{2}\gamma_i} + \frac{\mathbb{B}_{13}\gamma_i^{p-\frac{1}{2}}}{(\beta_n - \varpi\gamma_i)^p} e^{-\frac{g_3}{3}\gamma_i} \right. \\ & \left. - \frac{\mathbb{B}_{14}\gamma_i^{p-\frac{1}{2}}}{(\beta_n - \varpi\gamma_i)^p} e^{-\frac{g_3}{6}\gamma_i} - \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{g_3}{3}\right)^t \frac{\mathbb{B}_{15}\gamma_i^{t+p}}{(\beta_n - \varpi\gamma_i)^p} e^{-\frac{2g_3}{3}\gamma_i} + \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \frac{\mathbb{B}_{16}\mathbb{B}_{17}\gamma_i^{t+p}}{(\beta_n - \varpi\gamma_i)^p} e^{-\frac{2g_3}{3}\gamma_i} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}_f^{\text{LB}} = & \Pr[\Lambda_f^{\text{UB}} < \Lambda_{\text{thf}}] = \Pr\left[\min\left(\frac{\beta_f}{\vartheta}, \frac{\zeta_f \beta_f \alpha^2 |\mathbf{h}_{s_j r} \Phi \mathbf{h}_{\text{rf}}|^2}{\lambda |\mathbf{h}_{\text{rf}} \Phi|^2}, \zeta_f \beta_f \alpha^2 |\mathbf{h}_{s_j r} \Phi \mathbf{h}_{\text{rf}}|^2\right) < \Lambda_{\text{thf}}\right] \\ & = 1 - \mathcal{I}_f \left\{ 1 - \Pr\left[\underbrace{\frac{\zeta_f \beta_f \alpha^2 |\mathbf{h}_{s_j r} \Phi \mathbf{h}_{\text{rf}}|^2}{\lambda |\mathbf{h}_{\text{rf}} \Phi|^2} < \Lambda_{\text{thf}}}_{\mathcal{I}_1}\right]\right\} \left\{ 1 - \Pr\left[\underbrace{\zeta_f \beta_f \alpha^2 |\mathbf{h}_{s_j r} \Phi \mathbf{h}_{\text{rf}}|^2 < \Lambda_{\text{thf}}}_{\mathcal{I}_2}\right]\right\} \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

where $\Psi_1 = \binom{N_s}{q} \frac{(-1)^q \tau_p^q}{\sqrt{\pi} \Gamma(m_{\text{rf}} R)} \left(\frac{m_{\text{rf}}}{\Omega_{\text{rf}}}\right)^{-\frac{p}{2}}$, $\alpha_1 = \frac{q^2 \lambda \Omega_{\text{rf}}}{4 m_{\text{rf}} \Delta^2 \alpha^2 \beta_f \zeta_f}$, and $\mathcal{A}_4 = \left(\frac{m_{\text{rf}}}{\Omega_{\text{rf}}}\right)^{-\frac{\mu N_s}{2}} \frac{\Gamma(m_{\text{rf}} R + \frac{\mu N_s}{2})}{(\mu \Gamma(\mu))^{N_s} \Gamma(m_{\text{rf}} R)} \left(\frac{1}{\Delta} \sqrt{\frac{\lambda}{\alpha^2 \beta_f}}\right)^{\mu N_s}$. The term τ_p^q recursively calculated as $\tau_0^q = (\chi_0)^q$, $\tau_1^q = q(\chi_1)$, $\tau_{q(\mu-1)}^q = (\chi_{\mu-1})^q$ for $0 \leq p \leq q(\mu-1)$, $\tau_p^q = \frac{1}{p\chi_0} \sum_{s=1}^p [(sq-p+s)\chi_s \tau_{p-s}^q]$ for $2 \leq p \leq (\mu-1)$, and $\tau_p^q = \frac{1}{p\chi_0} \sum_{s=1}^{\mu-1} [(sq-p+s)\chi_s \tau_{p-s}^q]$ for $\mu \leq p \leq q(\mu-1)$, where $\chi_p = \frac{1}{p!} \left(\frac{1}{\Delta} \sqrt{\frac{\lambda}{\alpha^2 \beta_f \zeta_f}}\right)^p$. The term $\mu = \frac{\delta^2}{\sigma^2}$ represents the shape parameter and $\Delta = \frac{\sigma^2}{\delta}$ represents the scale parameter with

$$\delta = R \frac{\Gamma(m_{\text{sr}} + \frac{1}{2}) \Gamma(m_{\text{rf}} + \frac{1}{2})}{\Gamma(m_{\text{sr}}) \Gamma(m_{\text{rf}})} \left(\frac{\Omega_{\text{sr}} \Omega_{\text{rf}}}{m_{\text{sr}} m_{\text{rf}}}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}, \quad (37)$$

$$\sigma^2 = R \Omega_{\text{sr}} \Omega_{\text{rf}} \left\{ 1 - \frac{1}{m_{\text{sr}} m_{\text{rf}}} \left(\frac{\Gamma(m_{\text{sr}} + \frac{1}{2}) \Gamma(m_{\text{rf}} + \frac{1}{2})}{\Gamma(m_{\text{sr}}) \Gamma(m_{\text{rf}})}\right)^2 \right\}. \quad (38)$$

Proof : Refer to Appendix B.

Corollary 1: For the Rayleigh fading channels, (37) and (38) can be simplified by taking $m_{\text{sr}} = m_{\text{rf}} = 1$ as $\delta = 0.785398R\sqrt{\Omega_{\text{sr}}\Omega_{\text{rf}}}$ and $\sigma^2 = 0.38315R\Omega_{\text{sr}}\Omega_{\text{rf}}$. Further, by employing the simplified parameters δ and σ^2 , one can obtain $\mu = 1.60995R$ and $\Delta = 0.487841\sqrt{\Omega_{\text{sr}}\Omega_{\text{rf}}}$.

Lemma 3: The terms \mathcal{I}_2 and \mathcal{I}_2^∞ are given respectively as

$$\mathcal{I}_2 = \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \Psi_2 \Lambda_{\text{thf}}^{\frac{su}{2}} \mathbf{G}_{0,2}^{2,0} \left[\alpha_2 \Lambda_{\text{thf}} \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}} \right], \quad (39)$$

$$\mathcal{I}_2^\infty \approx \mathcal{A}_5 \Lambda_{\text{thf}}^{\frac{\mu N_s}{2}} \zeta_f^{-\frac{\mu N_s}{2}}, \quad (40)$$

where $\Psi_2 = \binom{N_s}{u} \frac{(-1)^u \tau_s^u}{\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{1}{N_s}$, $\alpha_2 = \frac{u^2}{4\Delta^2 \alpha^2 \beta_f \zeta_f}$, and $\mathcal{A}_5 = \left\{ \frac{1}{\mu \Gamma(\mu)} \left(\frac{1}{\Delta} \sqrt{\frac{\lambda}{\alpha^2 \beta_f}}\right)^\mu \right\}^{N_s}$. The term τ_s^u recursively calculated as $\tau_0^u = (\zeta_0)^u$, $\tau_1^u = u(\zeta_1)$, $\tau_{u(\mu-1)}^u = (\zeta_{\mu-1})^u$ for $0 \leq s \leq u(\mu-1)$, $\tau_s^u = \frac{1}{s\zeta_0} \sum_{p=1}^s [(pu-s+p)\zeta_p \tau_{s-p}^u]$ for $2 \leq s \leq (\mu-1)$, and $\tau_s^u = \frac{1}{s\zeta_0} \sum_{p=1}^{\mu-1} [(pu-s+p)\zeta_p \tau_{s-p}^u]$ for $\mu \leq s \leq u(\mu-1)$, where $\zeta_s = \frac{1}{s!} \left(\frac{1}{\Delta} \sqrt{\frac{\lambda}{\alpha^2 \beta_f \zeta_f}}\right)^s$.

Proof : Refer to Appendix C.

On invoking (35) and (39) in (33), the OP of the FU is given as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}_f^{\text{LB}} = & \sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \Psi_1 \Lambda_{\text{thf}}^{\frac{pq}{2}} \mathbf{G}_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\alpha_1 \Lambda_{\text{thf}} \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{1-\frac{p}{2}-m_{\text{rf}}R} \right] + \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \\ & \times \Psi_2 \Lambda_{\text{thf}}^{\frac{su}{2}} \mathbf{G}_{0,2}^{2,0} \left[\alpha_2 \Lambda_{\text{thf}} \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}} \right] - \sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \Psi_1 \Psi_2 \\ & \times \Lambda_{\text{thf}}^{\frac{pq}{2} + \frac{su}{2}} \mathbf{G}_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\alpha_1 \Lambda_{\text{thf}} \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{1-\frac{p}{2}-m_{\text{rf}}R} \right] \mathbf{G}_{0,2}^{2,0} \left[\alpha_2 \Lambda_{\text{thf}} \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}} \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

From (41), it is noted that the OP depends on the fading mitigation parameter of the BS-RIS m_{sr} and RIS-FU m_{rf} links, level of impairments ϕ_s and ϕ_f , power allocation coefficient for the NU β_n and the FU β_f , target rate of the FU \mathcal{R}_f , number of transmit antennas N_s at the BS, amplification gain α , and the number of REs R .

Further, the asymptotic OP closed-form expression of the FU link is obtained by substituting (36) and (40) in (33), which is given as

$$\mathbb{P}_f^{\text{LB}, \infty} \approx \mathcal{A}_{f1} \Lambda_{\text{thf}}^{\frac{\mu N_s}{2}} \zeta_f^{-\frac{\mu N_s}{2}} - \mathcal{A}_{f2} \Lambda_{\text{thf}}^{\mu N_s} \zeta_f^{-\mu N_s}, \quad (42)$$

where $\mathcal{A}_{f1} = \mathcal{A}_4 + \mathcal{A}_5$ and $\mathcal{A}_{f2} = \mathcal{A}_4 \mathcal{A}_5$. From (42), the diversity order is given as $\min\{\frac{\mu N_s}{2}, \mu N_s\} = \frac{\mu N_s}{2}$, which depends on the number of REs, the number of transmit antennas at the BS, and fading mitigation parameters of the BS-RIS and RIS-FU links. Note that the diversity order of the FU in the case of the Rayleigh fading channels is $0.804973RN_s$, which scales linearly with the number of REs RN_s .

B. Ergodic Capacity

The ergodic capacity of the FU is given as [14]

$$C_f = \mathbb{E} \{\log_2(1 + \Lambda_f)\} = \int_0^\infty \log_2(1 + \gamma) f_{\Lambda_f^{\text{UB}}}(\gamma) d\gamma. \quad (43)$$

The PDF $f_{\Lambda_f^{\text{UB}}}(\gamma)$ is obtained by differentiating (41) using [49, eq. (07.34.20.0017.02)], and is given as (44). On invoking (44) in (43) and representing $\log_2(1 + \gamma) = G_{2,2}^{1,2} \left[\gamma \middle| \begin{smallmatrix} 1,1 \\ 1,0 \end{smallmatrix} \right]$ and by employing the GCQ approximation method, the ergodic capacity is obtained as (45). From (45), it is observed that the ergodic capacity relies on the parameters m_{sr} , m_{rf} , ϕ_s , ϕ_f , β_n , β_f , N_s , α , and R .

The asymptotic ergodic capacity is approximated as

$$C_f^\infty \approx \mathbb{E} \{\log_2(\Lambda_f)\} = \log_2 \left(\int_0^\infty \gamma f_{\Lambda_f^{\text{UB}}}(\gamma) d\gamma \right). \quad (46)$$

On invoking (44) in (46) and using the GCQ approximation method, the asymptotic ergodic capacity is obtained as (47).

C. Average Symbol Error Rate

The generalized ASER expression for any modulation scheme is given as [8], [10]

$$\mathbb{P}_{e,f} = - \int_0^\infty \mathcal{P}'_s(e|\gamma) \mathbb{P}_f^{\text{LB}}(\gamma) d\gamma. \quad (48)$$

1) *Rectangular QAM*: On invoking the first-order derivative of the conditional SEP for rectangular QAM (17) and OP of the FU (41) in (48), and by employing [49, eq. (07.34.21.0088.01)] and the GCQ approximation method, the ASER for rectangular QAM is obtained as (49).

The asymptotic ASER is derived by substituting (17) and (42) in (48) and using [38, eq. (3.381.4)], which is given as

$$\mathbb{P}_{e,f}^{\text{RQAM},\infty} \approx \mathcal{A}_6 \zeta_f^{-\frac{\mu N_s}{2}} + \mathcal{A}_7 \zeta_f^{-\mu N_s}, \quad (50)$$

where \mathcal{A}_6 and \mathcal{A}_7 are given in (51) and (52), respectively. From (50), the diversity order is given as $\min\{\frac{\mu N_s}{2}, \mu N_s\} = \frac{\mu N_s}{2}$, which depends on the number of REs, the number of transmit antennas at the BS, and fading mitigation parameters of the BS-RIS and RIS-FU links.

2) *Cross QAM*: Substituting the first-order derivative of the conditional SEP for cross QAM (23) and OP of the FU (41) in (48), and by using [49, eq. (07.34.21.0088.01)] and the GCQ approximation method the closed-form expression of ASER for cross QAM is obtained as (53).

The asymptotic ASER is obtained by substituting (23) and (42) in (48) and using [38, eq. (3.381.4)], which is given as

$$\mathbb{P}_{e,f}^{\text{XQAM},\infty} \approx \mathcal{A}_8 \zeta_f^{-\frac{\mu N_s}{2}} + \mathcal{A}_9 \zeta_f^{-\mu N_s} \quad (54)$$

where \mathcal{A}_8 and \mathcal{A}_9 are given in (55) and (56), respectively. From (54), the diversity order is given as $\min\{\frac{\mu N_s}{2}, \mu N_s\} = \frac{\mu N_s}{2}$.

TABLE I: Closed-form expressions derived for both the NU and the FU.

Performance metric	NU	FU
OP	(7)	(41)
Asymptotic OP	(8)	(42)
Ergodic capacity	(12)	(45)
Asymptotic ergodic capacity	(14)	(47)
ASER (Rectangular QAM)	(18)	(49)
Asymptotic ASER (Rectangular QAM)	(20)	(50)
ASER (Cross QAM)	(24)	(53)
Asymptotic ASER (Cross QAM)	(25)	(54)
ASER (Hexagonal QAM)	(29)	(57)
Asymptotic ASER (Hexagonal QAM)	(30)	(58)

3) *Hexagonal QAM*: On invoking the first-order derivative of the conditional SEP for hexagonal QAM (28) and OP of the FU (41) in (48), and by using [49, eq. (07.34.21.0088.01)] and the GCQ approximation method, the ASER for hexagonal QAM is obtained as (57).

The asymptotic ASER is derived by substituting (28) and (42) in (48) and using [38, eq. (3.381.4)], which is given as

$$\mathbb{P}_{e,f}^{\text{HQAM},\infty} \approx \mathcal{A}_{10} \zeta_f^{-\frac{\mu N_s}{2}} + \mathcal{A}_{11} \zeta_f^{-\mu N_s}, \quad (58)$$

where the terms \mathcal{A}_{10} and \mathcal{A}_{11} are defined in (59) and (60), respectively. From (58), the diversity order is given as $\min\{\frac{\mu N_s}{2}, \mu N_s\} = \frac{\mu N_s}{2}$.

V. NUMERICAL AND SIMULATION RESULTS

This section details numerical results for assessing performance of the considered network. Accuracy of the derived closed-form expressions (OP, asymptotic OP, ergodic capacity, asymptotic ergodic capacity, ASER, and asymptotic ASER) are validated through Monte-Carlo simulations. The expressions for OP, ergodic capacity, and ASER derived throughout the paper for both the NU and the FU are summarized in Table I. The distances between BS-NU, BS-active RIS, and active RIS-FU are set to 10 m, 40 m, and 10 m, respectively [14]. A distance-dependent path-loss model is considered for all channels, specifically $\Omega_{ij} = d_{ij}^{-\alpha}$ where d_{ij} represents the distance between the nodes i and j , and $\{i, j\} \in \{\text{BS, NU, FU, active RIS}\}$ [14]. We set $\alpha = 2$ dB, $\beta_n = 0.3$, $\beta_f = 0.7$, $\sigma_n^2 = \sigma_f^2 = \sigma_r^2 = -50$ dBm [2], [29], $\phi_s = \phi_n = \phi_f = \phi = 0.1$, and $\rho = 0.15$ [43] unless specified. The fading mitigation parameters m_{sr} and m_{rf} are denoted as $\{m_{sr}, m_{rf}\}$ in the figures, and we consider $\mathcal{R}_n = \mathcal{R}_f = r_{\text{th}}$ for simplicity.

The numerical and simulation results illustrated here exhibit a perfect match, thereby confirming the accuracy of the derived closed-form expressions. Please note that OMA is a special case of NOMA and for a fair comparison both the NU and FU shares half of the resource block, and set $\Lambda_{\text{thf}} = 2^{2\mathcal{R}_f} - 1$ and $\Lambda_{\text{thn}} = 2^{2\mathcal{R}_n} - 1$. Furthermore, the system performance with a passive RIS is derived by setting $\alpha_r = 1$ and $\sigma_r^2 = 0$.

A. Near User

Fig. 2 depicts NU OP versus transmit power for $\sigma_n^2 = -30$ dBm and $N_s = 2$. The numerical results align seamlessly with the simulation results, confirming the accuracy of the derived closed-form expression (7). Indeed, the asymptotic

$$\begin{aligned}
f_{\Lambda_f^{\text{LB}}}(\gamma) &= \sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \Psi_1 \gamma^{\frac{pq}{2}-1} \left\{ \frac{pq}{2} G_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\alpha_1 \gamma \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{1-\frac{p}{2}-m_{\text{tr}}R} \right] + G_{2,3}^{2,2} \left[\alpha_1 \gamma \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}, 1}^{1-\frac{p}{2}-m_{\text{tr}}R} \right] \right\} + \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \Psi_2 \gamma^{\frac{su}{2}-1} \left\{ \frac{su}{2} G_{0,2}^{2,0} \left[\alpha_2 \gamma \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}} \right] \right. \\
&\quad \left. + G_{1,3}^{2,1} \left[\alpha_2 \gamma \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}, 1}^0 \right] \right\} - \sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \Psi_1 \Psi_2 \gamma^{\frac{pq}{2} + \frac{su}{2} - 1} \left\{ \left(\frac{pq}{2} + \frac{su}{2} \right) G_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\alpha_1 \gamma \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{1-\frac{p}{2}-m_{\text{tr}}R} \right] G_{0,2}^{2,0} \left[\alpha_2 \gamma \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}} \right] \right. \\
&\quad \left. + G_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\alpha_1 \gamma \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{1-\frac{p}{2}-m_{\text{tr}}R} \right] G_{1,3}^{2,1} \left[\alpha_2 \gamma \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}, 1}^0 \right] + G_{2,3}^{2,2} \left[\alpha_1 \gamma \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}, 1}^{0, 1-\frac{p}{2}-m_{\text{tr}}R} \right] G_{0,2}^{2,0} \left[\alpha_2 \gamma \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}} \right] \right\} \quad (44)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{C}_f &\approx \sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \sum_{i=1}^H \Psi_i \Psi_1 \gamma_i^{\frac{pq}{2}-1} \left\{ \frac{pq}{2} G_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\alpha_1 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{1-\frac{p}{2}-m_{\text{tr}}R} \right] + G_{2,3}^{2,2} \left[\alpha_1 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}, 1}^{0, 1-\frac{p}{2}-m_{\text{tr}}R} \right] \right\} G_{2,2}^{1,2} \left[\gamma_i \Big|_{1,0}^{1,1} \right] + \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \sum_{i=1}^H \Psi_i \Psi_2 \\
&\quad \times \gamma_i^{\frac{su}{2}-1} \left\{ \frac{su}{2} G_{0,2}^{2,0} \left[\alpha_2 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}} \right] + G_{1,3}^{2,1} \left[\alpha_2 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}, 1}^0 \right] \right\} G_{2,2}^{1,2} \left[\gamma_i \Big|_{1,0}^{1,1} \right] - \sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \sum_{i=1}^H \Psi_i \Psi_1 \Psi_2 \gamma_i^{\frac{pq}{2} + \frac{su}{2} - 1} \\
&\quad \times \left\{ \left(\frac{pq}{2} + \frac{su}{2} \right) G_{0,2}^{2,0} \left[\alpha_2 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}} \right] G_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\alpha_1 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{1-\frac{p}{2}-m_{\text{tr}}R} \right] + G_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\alpha_1 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{1-\frac{p}{2}-m_{\text{tr}}R} \right] G_{1,3}^{2,1} \left[\alpha_2 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}, 1}^0 \right] + G_{0,2}^{2,0} \left[\alpha_2 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}} \right] \right. \\
&\quad \left. \times G_{2,3}^{2,2} \left[\alpha_1 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}, 1}^{0, 1-\frac{p}{2}-m_{\text{tr}}R} \right] \right\} G_{2,2}^{1,2} \left[\gamma_i \Big|_{1,0}^{1,1} \right] \quad (45)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{C}_f^\infty &\approx \log_2 \left(\sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \sum_{i=1}^H \Psi_i \Psi_1 \gamma_i^{\frac{pq}{2}} \left\{ \frac{pq}{2} G_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\alpha_1 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{1-\frac{p}{2}-m_{\text{tr}}R} \right] + G_{2,3}^{2,2} \left[\alpha_1 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}, 1}^{0, 1-\frac{p}{2}-m_{\text{tr}}R} \right] \right\} + \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \sum_{i=1}^H \Psi_i \Psi_2 \gamma_i^{\frac{su}{2}} \right. \\
&\quad \times \left\{ \frac{su}{2} G_{0,2}^{2,0} \left[\alpha_2 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}} \right] + G_{1,3}^{2,1} \left[\alpha_2 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}, 1}^0 \right] \right\} - \sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \sum_{i=1}^H \Psi_i \Psi_1 \Psi_2 \gamma_i^{\frac{pq}{2} + \frac{su}{2}} \left\{ \left(\frac{pq}{2} + \frac{su}{2} \right) G_{0,2}^{2,0} \left[\alpha_2 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}} \right] \right. \\
&\quad \left. \times G_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\alpha_1 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{1-\frac{p}{2}-m_{\text{tr}}R} \right] + G_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\alpha_1 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{1-\frac{p}{2}-m_{\text{tr}}R} \right] G_{1,3}^{2,1} \left[\alpha_2 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}, 1}^0 \right] + G_{0,2}^{2,0} \left[\alpha_2 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}} \right] G_{2,3}^{2,2} \left[\alpha_1 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}, 1}^{0, 1-\frac{p}{2}-m_{\text{tr}}R} \right] \right\} \Big) \quad (47)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{P}_{\text{e,f}}^{\text{RQAM}} &\approx \mathbb{B}_1 \left[- \sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \Psi_1 \left(\frac{c_3^2}{2} \right)^{-\left(\frac{pq}{2} + \frac{1}{2}\right)} G_{2,2}^{2,2} \left[\frac{2\alpha_1}{c_3^2} \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{1}{2} - \frac{pq}{2}, 1 - \frac{p}{2} - m_{\text{tr}}R} \right] - \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \Psi_2 \left(\frac{c_3^2}{2} \right)^{-\left(\frac{su}{2} + \frac{1}{2}\right)} G_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\frac{2\alpha_2}{c_3^2} \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{1}{2} - \frac{su}{2}} \right] \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \sum_{i=1}^H \Psi_i \Psi_1 \Psi_2 \gamma_i^{\frac{pq+su-1}{2}} e^{-\frac{c_3^2}{2} \gamma_i} G_{0,2}^{2,0} \left[\alpha_2 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}} \right] G_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\alpha_1 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{1-\frac{p}{2}-m_{\text{tr}}R} \right] + \mathbb{B}_2 \left[- \sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \Psi_1 \right. \right. \\
&\quad \times \left(\frac{c_4^2}{2} \right)^{-\left(\frac{pq}{2} + \frac{1}{2}\right)} G_{2,2}^{2,2} \left[\frac{2\alpha_1}{c_4^2} \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{1}{2} - \frac{pq}{2}, 1 - \frac{p}{2} - m_{\text{tr}}R} \right] - \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \Psi_2 \left(\frac{c_4^2}{2} \right)^{-\left(\frac{su}{2} + \frac{1}{2}\right)} G_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\frac{2\alpha_2}{c_4^2} \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{1}{2} - \frac{su}{2}} \right] + \sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \sum_{i=1}^H \\
&\quad \times \Psi_i \Psi_1 \Psi_2 \gamma_i^{\frac{pq+su-1}{2}} e^{-\frac{c_4^2}{2} \gamma_i} G_{0,2}^{2,0} \left[\alpha_2 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}} \right] G_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\alpha_1 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{1-\frac{p}{2}-m_{\text{tr}}R} \right] + \mathbb{B}_3 \left[\sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \Psi_1 \mathbb{B}_4 \left(\frac{c_3^2 + c_4^2}{2} \right)^{-\frac{pq}{2} - t - 1} \right. \\
&\quad \times G_{2,2}^{2,2} \left[\frac{2\alpha_1}{c_3^2 + c_4^2} \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{1}{2} - \frac{pq}{2} - t, 1 - \frac{p}{2} - m_{\text{tr}}R} \right] + \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \Psi_2 \mathbb{B}_4 \left(\frac{c_3^2 + c_4^2}{2} \right)^{-\frac{su}{2} - t - 1} G_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\frac{2\alpha_2}{c_3^2 + c_4^2} \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{1}{2} - \frac{su}{2} - t} \right] \\
&\quad \left. - \sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \sum_{i=1}^H \Psi_i \Psi_1 \Psi_2 \mathbb{B}_4 \gamma_i^{\frac{pq+su}{2} + t} e^{-\frac{c_3^2 + c_4^2}{2} \gamma_i} G_{0,2}^{2,0} \left[\alpha_2 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}} \right] G_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\alpha_1 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{1-\frac{p}{2}-m_{\text{tr}}R} \right] \right] \quad (49)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\mathcal{A}_6 = \mathcal{A}_{f1} \left[\Gamma \left(\frac{\mu N_s + 1}{2} \right) \left\{ -\mathbb{B}_1 \left(\frac{c_3^2}{2} \right)^{-\frac{\mu N_s + 1}{2}} - \mathbb{B}_2 \left(\frac{c_4^2}{2} \right)^{-\frac{\mu N_s + 1}{2}} \right\} + \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \mathbb{B}_3 \mathbb{B}_4 \left(\frac{c_3^2 + c_4^2}{2} \right)^{-\frac{\mu N_s + 2t + 2}{2}} \Gamma \left(\frac{\mu N_s + 2t + 2}{2} \right) \right] \quad (51)$$

$$\mathcal{A}_7 = \mathcal{A}_{f2} \left[\Gamma \left(\frac{2\mu N_s + 1}{2} \right) \left\{ \mathbb{B}_1 \left(\frac{c_3^2}{2} \right)^{-\frac{2\mu N_s + 1}{2}} + \mathbb{B}_2 \left(\frac{c_4^2}{2} \right)^{-\frac{2\mu N_s + 1}{2}} \right\} - \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \mathbb{B}_3 \mathbb{B}_4 \left(\frac{c_3^2 + c_4^2}{2} \right)^{-\mu N_s + t + 1} \Gamma(\mu N_s + t + 1) \right] \quad (52)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{P}_{e,f}^{\text{XQAM}} \approx & \mathbb{B}_5 \left[- \sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \Psi_1 \left(\frac{1}{k_2} \right)^{-\left(\frac{pq}{2} + \frac{1}{2}\right)} \mathbf{G}_{2,2}^{2,2} \left[\alpha_1 k_2 \middle|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{-\frac{pq}{2}, 1 - \frac{p}{2} - m_{\text{tr}} R} \right] - \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \Psi_2 \left(\frac{1}{k_2} \right)^{-\left(\frac{su}{2} + \frac{1}{2}\right)} \mathbf{G}_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\alpha_2 k_2 \middle|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{-\frac{su}{2}} \right] \right. \\
& + \sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \sum_{i=1}^H \Psi_i \Psi_1 \Psi_2 \gamma_i^{\frac{pq+su-1}{2}} e^{-\frac{1}{k_2} \gamma_i} \mathbf{G}_{0,2}^{2,0} \left[\alpha_2 \gamma_i \middle|_{0, \frac{1}{2}} \right] \mathbf{G}_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\alpha_1 \gamma_i \middle|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{1 - \frac{p}{2} - m_{\text{tr}} R} \right] \left. + \mathbb{B}_6 \left[\sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \Psi_1 \left(\frac{k_3^2}{k_2} \right)^{-\left(\frac{pq}{2} + \frac{1}{2}\right)} \right. \right. \\
& \times \mathbf{G}_{2,2}^{2,2} \left[\frac{\alpha_1 k_2}{k_3^2} \middle|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{-\frac{pq}{2}, 1 - \frac{p}{2} - m_{\text{tr}} R} \right] + \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \Psi_2 \left(\frac{k_3^2}{k_2} \right)^{-\left(\frac{su}{2} + \frac{1}{2}\right)} \mathbf{G}_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\frac{\alpha_2 k_2}{k_3^2} \middle|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{-\frac{su}{2}} \right] - \sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \sum_{i=1}^H \Psi_i \Psi_1 \Psi_2 \gamma_i^{\frac{pq+su-1}{2}} \\
& \times e^{-\frac{k_3^2}{k_2} \gamma_i} \mathbf{G}_{0,2}^{2,0} \left[\alpha_2 \gamma_i \middle|_{0, \frac{1}{2}} \right] \mathbf{G}_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\alpha_1 \gamma_i \middle|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{1 - \frac{p}{2} - m_{\text{tr}} R} \right] \left. + \mathbb{B}_7 \left[\sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \sum_{u=1}^{\frac{k_3}{2}-1} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \Psi_1 \mathbb{B}\mathbb{B}_{10} (k_6)^{-\left(\frac{pq}{2} + t + 1\right)} \mathbf{G}_{2,2}^{2,2} \left[\frac{\alpha_1}{k_6} \middle|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{-\frac{pq}{2} - t, 1 - \frac{p}{2} - m_{\text{tr}} R} \right] \right. \right. \\
& + \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \sum_{u=1}^{\frac{k_3}{2}-1} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \Psi_2 \mathbb{B}\mathbb{B}_{10} (k_6)^{-\frac{su}{2} - t - 1} \mathbf{G}_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\frac{\alpha_2}{k_6} \middle|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{-\frac{su}{2} - t} \right] - \sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \sum_{u=1}^{\frac{k_3}{2}-1} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \sum_{i=1}^H \Psi_i \Psi_1 \Psi_2 \mathbb{B}\mathbb{B}_{10} \gamma_i^{\frac{pq+su}{2} + t} e^{-k_6 \gamma_i} \\
& \times \mathbf{G}_{0,2}^{2,0} \left[\alpha_2 \gamma_i \middle|_{0, \frac{1}{2}} \right] \mathbf{G}_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\alpha_1 \gamma_i \middle|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{1 - \frac{p}{2} - m_{\text{tr}} R} \right] \left. + \mathbb{B}_8 \left[\sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \Psi_1 \mathbb{B}\mathbb{B}_{11} \left(\frac{1 + k_3^2}{k_2} \right)^{-\left(\frac{pq}{2} + t + 1\right)} \mathbf{G}_{2,2}^{2,2} \left[\frac{\alpha_1 k_2}{1 + k_3^2} \middle|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{-\frac{pq}{2} - t, 1 - \frac{p}{2} - m_{\text{tr}} R} \right] \right. \right. \\
& + \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \Psi_2 \mathbb{B}\mathbb{B}_{11} \left(\frac{1 + k_3^2}{k_2} \right)^{-\frac{su}{2} - t - 1} \mathbf{G}_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\frac{\alpha_2 k_2}{1 + k_3^2} \middle|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{-\frac{su}{2} - t} \right] - \sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \sum_{i=1}^H \Psi_i \Psi_1 \Psi_2 \mathbb{B}\mathbb{B}_{11} \gamma_i^{\frac{pq+su}{2} + t} \\
& \times e^{-\frac{1+k_3^2}{k_2} \gamma_i} \mathbf{G}_{0,2}^{2,0} \left[\alpha_2 \gamma_i \middle|_{0, \frac{1}{2}} \right] \mathbf{G}_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\alpha_1 \gamma_i \middle|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{1 - \frac{p}{2} - m_{\text{tr}} R} \right] \left. + \mathbb{B}_9 \left[\sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \Psi_1 \mathbb{B} \left(\frac{1}{k_2} \right)^t \left(\frac{2}{k_2} \right)^{-\frac{pq}{2} - t - 1} \right. \right. \\
& \times \mathbf{G}_{2,2}^{2,2} \left[\frac{\alpha_1 k_2}{2} \middle|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{-\frac{pq}{2} - t, 1 - \frac{p}{2} - m_{\text{tr}} R} \right] + \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \Psi_2 \mathbb{B} \left(\frac{1}{k_2} \right)^t \left(\frac{2}{k_2} \right)^{-\frac{su}{2} - t - 1} \mathbf{G}_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\frac{\alpha_2 k_2}{2} \middle|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{-\frac{su}{2} - t} \right] \\
& \left. - \sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \sum_{i=1}^H \Psi_i \Psi_1 \Psi_2 \mathbb{B} \left(\frac{1}{k_2} \right)^t \gamma_i^{\frac{pq+su}{2} + t} e^{-\frac{2}{k_2} \gamma_i} \mathbf{G}_{0,2}^{2,0} \left[\alpha_2 \gamma_i \middle|_{0, \frac{1}{2}} \right] \mathbf{G}_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\alpha_1 \gamma_i \middle|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{1 - \frac{p}{2} - m_{\text{tr}} R} \right] \right] \quad (53)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{A}_8 = \mathcal{A}_{f1} \left[\Gamma \left(\frac{\mu N_s + 1}{2} \right) \left\{ -\mathbb{B}_5 \left(\frac{1}{k_2} \right)^{-\frac{\mu N_s + 1}{2}} + \mathbb{B}_6 \left(\frac{k_3^2}{k_2} \right)^{-\frac{\mu N_s + 1}{2}} \right\} + \sum_{u=1}^{\frac{k_3}{2}-1} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \mathbb{B}\mathbb{B}_7 \mathbb{B}_{10} k_6^{-\frac{\mu N_s + 2t + 2}{2}} \Gamma \left(\frac{\mu N_s + 2t + 2}{2} \right) \right. \\
\left. + \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \mathbb{B}\mathbb{B}_8 \mathbb{B}_{11} \left(\frac{1 + k_3^2}{k_2} \right)^{-\frac{\mu N_s + 2t + 2}{2}} \Gamma \left(\frac{\mu N_s + 2t + 2}{2} \right) + \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \mathbb{B}\mathbb{B}_9 \left(\frac{1}{k_2} \right)^t \left(\frac{2}{k_2} \right)^{-\frac{\mu N_s + 2t + 2}{2}} \Gamma \left(\frac{\mu N_s + 2t + 2}{2} \right) \right] \quad (55)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{A}_9 = \mathcal{A}_{f2} \left[\Gamma \left(\frac{2\mu N_s + 1}{2} \right) \left\{ \mathbb{B}_5 \left(\frac{1}{k_2} \right)^{-\frac{2\mu N_s + 1}{2}} - \mathbb{B}_6 \left(\frac{k_3^2}{k_2} \right)^{-\frac{2\mu N_s + 1}{2}} \right\} - \sum_{u=1}^{\frac{k_3}{2}-1} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \mathbb{B}\mathbb{B}_7 \mathbb{B}_{10} k_6^{-(\mu N_s + t + 1)} \Gamma (\mu N_s + t + 1) \right. \\
\left. - \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \mathbb{B}\mathbb{B}_8 \mathbb{B}_{11} \left(\frac{1 + k_3^2}{k_2} \right)^{-(\mu N_s + t + 1)} \Gamma (\mu N_s + t + 1) - \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \mathbb{B}\mathbb{B}_9 \left(\frac{1}{k_2} \right)^t \left(\frac{2}{k_2} \right)^{-(\mu N_s + t + 1)} \Gamma (\mu N_s + t + 1) \right] \quad (56)
\end{aligned}$$

OP matches the exact OP in the high-transmit SNR regimes, thus validating (8). An OP enhancement is noted as the fading mitigation parameter m_{sn} increases, as this corresponds to a better channel condition for signal transmission. To attain an OP of 10^{-2} , approximately 4.04 dB gain is achieved as the fading mitigation parameter m_{sn} increases from 1 to 2, with $r_{\text{th}} = 1$ bps/Hz. Further, note that the outage performance improves with a decrease in r_{th} since a lower target rate leads to a relatively lower target SNR. This insight is useful for designing a communication setup with a desired target rate. Furthermore, it is noticed that the NOMA outperforms the

OMA. For $m_{\text{sn}} = 1$ and 2, the considered NOMA network respectively saves approximately 0.28 and 0.33 dB in transmit power with respect to OMA to attain an OP of 10^{-2} with $r_{\text{th}} = 1$ bps/Hz.

Fig. 3 illustrates OP versus transmit power under various transmit antennas N_s at the BS. An OP enhancement is noted with an increase in N_s . This enhancement is achieved due to the improvement in transmit diversity gain. To attain an OP of 10^{-2} with $\rho = 0$, approximately 7.62 and 9.63 dB gains are achieved when N_s increases from 1 to 3 and 5, respectively. While an OP degradation is noted with ipSIC. To achieve an

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{P}_{e,f}^{\text{HQAM}} \approx & \mathbb{B}_{12} \left[- \sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \Psi_1 \left(\frac{g_3}{2} \right)^{-\left(\frac{pq}{2} + \frac{1}{2}\right)} \mathbf{G}_{2,2}^{2,2} \left[\frac{2\alpha_1}{g_3} \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{1}{2} - \frac{pq}{2}, 1 - \frac{p}{2} - m_{\text{tr}}R} \right] - \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \Psi_2 \left(\frac{g_3}{2} \right)^{-\left(\frac{su}{2} + \frac{1}{2}\right)} \mathbf{G}_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\frac{2\alpha_2}{g_3} \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{1}{2} - \frac{su}{2}} \right] \right. \\
& + \sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \sum_{i=1}^H \Psi_i \Psi_1 \Psi_2 \gamma_i^{\frac{pq+su-1}{2}} e^{-\frac{g_3}{2} \gamma_i} \mathbf{G}_{0,2}^{2,0} \left[\alpha_2 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}} \right] \mathbf{G}_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\alpha_1 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{1 - \frac{p}{2} - m_{\text{tr}}R} \right] \left. + \mathbb{B}_{13} \left[\sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \Psi_1 \right. \right. \\
& \times \left(\frac{g_3}{3} \right)^{-\left(\frac{pq}{2} + \frac{1}{2}\right)} \mathbf{G}_{2,2}^{2,2} \left[\frac{3\alpha_1}{g_3} \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{1}{2} - \frac{pq}{2}, 1 - \frac{p}{2} - m_{\text{tr}}R} \right] + \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \Psi_2 \left(\frac{g_3}{3} \right)^{-\left(\frac{su}{2} + \frac{1}{2}\right)} \mathbf{G}_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\frac{3\alpha_2}{g_3} \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{1}{2} - \frac{su}{2}} \right] \\
& - \sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \sum_{i=1}^H \Psi_i \Psi_1 \Psi_2 \gamma_i^{\frac{pq+su-1}{2}} e^{-\frac{g_3}{3} \gamma_i} \mathbf{G}_{0,2}^{2,0} \left[\alpha_2 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}} \right] \mathbf{G}_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\alpha_1 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{1 - \frac{p}{2} - m_{\text{tr}}R} \right] \left. + \mathbb{B}_{14} \left[- \sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \Psi_1 \right. \right. \\
& \times \left(\frac{g_3}{6} \right)^{-\left(\frac{pq}{2} + \frac{1}{2}\right)} \mathbf{G}_{2,2}^{2,2} \left[\frac{6\alpha_1}{g_3} \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{1}{2} - \frac{pq}{2}, 1 - \frac{p}{2} - m_{\text{tr}}R} \right] - \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \Psi_2 \left(\frac{g_3}{6} \right)^{-\frac{su}{2} - \frac{1}{2}} \mathbf{G}_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\frac{6\alpha_2}{g_3} \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{-\frac{su}{2} - \frac{1}{2}} \right] \\
& + \sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \sum_{i=1}^H \Psi_i \Psi_1 \Psi_2 \gamma_i^{\frac{pq+su}{2} - \frac{1}{2}} e^{-\frac{g_3}{6} \gamma_i} \mathbf{G}_{0,2}^{2,0} \left[\alpha_2 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}} \right] \mathbf{G}_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\alpha_1 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{1 - \frac{p}{2} - m_{\text{tr}}R} \right] \left. + \mathbb{B}_{15} \left[- \sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \Psi_1 \right. \right. \\
& \times \mathbb{B} \left(\frac{g_3}{3} \right)^t \left(\frac{2g_3}{3} \right)^{-\left(\frac{pq}{2} + t + 1\right)} \mathbf{G}_{2,2}^{2,2} \left[\frac{3\alpha_1}{2g_3} \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{pq}{2} - t, 1 - \frac{p}{2} - m_{\text{tr}}R} \right] - \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \Psi_2 \mathbb{B} \left(\frac{g_3}{3} \right)^t \left(\frac{2g_3}{3} \right)^{-\left(\frac{pq}{2} + t + 1\right)} \\
& \times \mathbf{G}_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\frac{3\alpha_2}{2g_3} \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{-\frac{su}{2} - t} \right] - \sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \sum_{i=1}^H \Psi_i \Psi_1 \Psi_2 \mathbb{B} \left(\frac{g_3}{3} \right)^t \gamma_i^{\frac{pq+su}{2} + t} e^{-\frac{2g_3}{3} \gamma_i} \mathbf{G}_{0,2}^{2,0} \left[\alpha_2 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}} \right] \\
& \times \mathbf{G}_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\alpha_1 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{1 - \frac{p}{2} - m_{\text{tr}}R} \right] \left. + \mathbb{B}_{15} \left[\sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \Psi_1 \mathbb{B}_{17} \left(\frac{2g_3}{3} \right)^{-\frac{pq}{2} - t - 1} \mathbf{G}_{2,2}^{2,2} \left[\frac{3\alpha_1}{2g_3} \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{pq}{2} - t, 1 - \frac{p}{2} - m_{\text{tr}}R} \right] \right. \right. \\
& + \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \Psi_2 \mathbb{B}_{17} \left\{ \left(\frac{g_3}{2} \right)^t + \left(\frac{g_3}{6} \right)^t \right\} \left(\frac{2g_3}{3} \right)^{-\frac{su}{2} - t - 1} \mathbf{G}_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\frac{3\alpha_2}{2g_3} \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{-\frac{su}{2} - t} \right] \\
& \left. - \sum_{q=0}^{N_s} \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} \sum_{p=0}^{q(\mu-1)} \sum_{s=0}^{u(\mu-1)} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \sum_{i=1}^H \Psi_i \Psi_1 \Psi_2 \mathbb{B}_{17} \gamma_i^{\frac{pq+su}{2} + t} e^{-\frac{2g_3}{3} \gamma_i} \mathbf{G}_{0,2}^{2,0} \left[\alpha_2 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}} \right] \mathbf{G}_{1,2}^{2,1} \left[\alpha_1 \gamma_i \Big|_{0, \frac{1}{2}}^{1 - \frac{p}{2} - m_{\text{tr}}R} \right] \right] \quad (57)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{A}_{10} = \mathcal{A}_{f1} \left[- \mathbb{B}_{12} \left(\frac{g_3}{2} \right)^{-\frac{\mu N_s + 1}{2}} \Gamma \left(\frac{\mu N_s + 1}{2} \right) + \mathbb{B}_{13} \left(\frac{g_3}{3} \right)^{-\frac{\mu N_s + 1}{2}} \Gamma \left(\frac{\mu N_s + 1}{2} \right) - \mathbb{B}_{14} \left(\frac{g_3}{6} \right)^{-\frac{\mu N_s + 1}{2}} \Gamma \left(\frac{\mu N_s + 1}{2} \right) \right. \\
\left. - \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \mathbb{B}_{15} \left(\frac{g_3}{3} \right)^t \left(\frac{2g_3}{3} \right)^{-\frac{\mu N_s + 2t + 2}{2}} \Gamma \left(\frac{\mu N_s + 2t + 2}{2} \right) + \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \mathbb{B}_{16} \mathbb{B}_{17} \left(\frac{2g_3}{3} \right)^{-\frac{\mu N_s + 2t + 2}{2}} \Gamma \left(\frac{\mu N_s + 2t + 2}{2} \right) \right] \quad (59)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{A}_{11} = \mathcal{A}_{f2} \left[\mathbb{B}_{12} \left(\frac{g_3}{2} \right)^{-\frac{2\mu N_s + 1}{2}} \Gamma \left(\frac{2\mu N_s + 1}{2} \right) - \mathbb{B}_{13} \left(\frac{g_3}{3} \right)^{-\frac{2\mu N_s + 1}{2}} \Gamma \left(\frac{2\mu N_s + 1}{2} \right) + \mathbb{B}_{14} \left(\frac{g_3}{6} \right)^{-\frac{2\mu N_s + 1}{2}} \Gamma \left(\frac{2\mu N_s + 1}{2} \right) \right. \\
\left. + \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \mathbb{B}_{15} \left(\frac{g_3}{3} \right)^t \left(\frac{2g_3}{3} \right)^{-(\mu N_s + t + 1)} \Gamma(\mu N_s + t + 1) - \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \mathbb{B}_{16} \mathbb{B}_{17} \left(\frac{2g_3}{3} \right)^{-(\mu N_s + t + 1)} \Gamma(\mu N_s + t + 1) \right] \quad (60)
\end{aligned}$$

OP of 10^{-2} , approximately 2.01 dB additional transmit power is required for an ipSIC as compared to a perfect SIC ($\rho = 0$).

Fig. 4 depicts the NU ergodic capacity versus transmit power under various fading mitigation parameter and hardware impairments. Again, the simulation results match the numerical results, thus validating (12). Indeed, the asymptotic ergodic capacity matches with ergodic capacity in the high transmit SNR regimes, thus validating (14). Notice that the ergodic capacity increases with transmit power P_s and the fading mitigation parameter m_{sn} . However, an degradation in ergodic

capacity performance is noted with hardware impairments. Furthermore, to achieve an ergodic capacity of 6 bps/Hz, the considered NOMA requires approximately 13.03 dB less power than OMA for $m_{\text{sn}} = 2$.

Fig. 5, Fig. 6, and Fig. 7 show the ASER versus transmit power curves of the NU under rectangular QAM, cross QAM, and hexagonal QAM schemes, respectively, with $N_s = 1$, $\rho = 0$ and $\phi = 0$. The numerical and simulation results align seamlessly, confirming the validity of (18), (24), and (29). Further, the asymptotic ASER matches the exact ASER in the high-transmit SNR regimes, thus validating (20), (25),

Fig. 2: Outage probability versus transmit power of NU with $\sigma_n^2 = -30$ dBm and $N_s = 2$.

Fig. 3: Outage probability versus transmit power of NU with $\sigma_n^2 = -30$ dBm.

and (30). The ASER performance is noted to enhance with m_{sn} due to the better channel conditions for signal transmission. Moreover, the ASER performance deteriorates with the increase in constellation size M . From Fig. 5, it is evident that to attain an ASER of 10^{-2} , approximately 6.45 and 13.56 dB power saving gains are achieved when M decreases from 128 to 32 and 8, respectively, with $m_{sn} = 1$. Further, from Fig. 6, it is noticed that when M decreases from 512 to 128 and 32, approximately 6.21 and 13.32 dB power saving gains are respectively achieved to attain an ASER of 10^{-2} with $m_{sn} = 1$. Furthermore, observe from Fig. 7 that to achieve an ASER of 10^{-2} , approximately 3.05, 6.19, 9.43, 12.97, 16.04, 19.74, and 24.16 dB power saving gains are achieved when M decreases from 512 to 256, 128, 64, 32, 16, 8, and 4, respectively, with $m_{sn} = 1$.

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Fig. 8 depicts FU OP versus transmit power for $R = 8$, $N_s = 1$, and $\phi = 0$. The numerical and simulation results exhibit a perfect match, confirming the accuracy of (41). Additionally, the asymptotic OP approaches the exact OP in the high transmit SNR regimes, validating the correctness of (42). Note that FU OP decreases with the fading mitigation parameters $\{m_{sr}, m_{tr}\}$ due to the increasingly better channel conditions for signal transmission. In order to achieve an OP of 10^{-2} , approximately 2.45 and 4.20 dB power saving gains are obtained as the fading mitigation parameters transition from $\{1, 1\}$ to $\{2, 1\}$ and $\{2, 2\}$, respectively, with $r_{th} = 1$ bps/Hz. Further, it is noticed that the OP performance improves with a decrease in target rate because a lower target rate demands a relatively lower SNR. Moreover, a notable OP improvement of

Fig. 4: Ergodic capacity versus transmit power of NU with $N_s = 1$ and $\rho = 0$.

Fig. 5: ASER versus transmit power of NU for a rectangular QAM with $N_s = 1$, $\rho = 0$ and $\phi = 0$.

NOMA over OMA can be observed. For the fading mitigation parameters $\{1, 1\}$, $\{2, 1\}$, and $\{2, 2\}$, NOMA attains respectively 6.16, 6.24, and 6.19 dB power saving gains compared with the OMA.

Fig. 9 depicts the positive impact of the number of transmit antennas N_s on the FU OP. This positive impact is attributed due to the fact that the diversity gain improves with N_s . To attain an OP of 10^{-2} , approximately 4.18 and 5.48 dB gains are achieved when N_s increases from 1 to 3 and 5, respectively.

Fig. 10 depicts the positive impact of the number of active REs on the FU OP. To attain an OP of 10^{-2} , approximately 9.59, 18.26, and 26.01, dB power saving gains are observed as R increases from 4 to 8, 16, and 32, respectively. This substantial improvement is achieved due to the enhanced signal strength and fine-grained reflect beamforming with increase in R , which can help in deploying a communication setup with a desired performance level in practice. Furthermore, the system with an active RIS achieves a significant performance gain over the passive RIS implementation in terms of transmit power saving P_s . Indeed, to attain an OP of 10^{-2} , approximately 6.41, 6.44, and 6.39 dB power saving gains are achieved for $R = 8, 16$, and 32, respectively.

Fig. 11 depicts the impact of the amplification gain α and thermal noise power σ_r^2 introduced by the active REs on the FU OP. Note that OP improves with α owing to the enhanced signal strength. To attain an OP of 10^{-2} , approximately 1.81, 3.87, and 5.80 dB power saving gains are achieved when α increases from 2 to 3, 4, and 5 dB, respectively, with $\sigma_r^2 = -50$ dBm. This suggests that the amplification gain achieved by the RIS can facilitate the practical deployment of an energy-efficient wireless communication system. Furthermore, OP

Fig. 6: ASER versus transmit power of NU for a cross QAM with $N_s = 1$, $\rho = 0$ and $\phi = 0$.

Fig. 7: ASER versus transmit power of NU for a hexagonal QAM with $N_s = 1$, $\rho = 0$ and $\phi = 0$.

decreases with a reduction in σ_r^2 . Indeed, when σ_r^2 reduces from -20 dBm to -30 and -50 dBm, respectively 9.68, and 13.09 dB power saving gains are observed to attain an OP of 10^{-1} with $\alpha = 2$ dB.

Fig. 12 depicts FU ergodic capacity versus transmit power for $R = 4$ and $\alpha = 2$ dB. The simulation results match the numerical results, thus validating (45). Indeed, the asymptotic ergodic capacity matches with ergodic capacity in the high transmit SNR regimes, thus validating (47). For the considered NOMA network, the ergodic capacity increases with the transmit power P_s in the low transmit power regime. As the transmit power further increases, NOMA performance reaches a saturation point. This is due to an increase in interference experienced by the NU. Nevertheless, in the low transmit power regime, NOMA outperforms OMA. It is noted that the ergodic capacity experiences improvement with better fading statistics.

Fig. 13 depicts FU ergodic capacity versus transmit power with fading mitigation parameter $\{2, 2\}$ while showing the performance improvement as the number of REs increases. Furthermore, the active RIS implementation outperforms the passive RIS one due to the amplification gain offered by the former. Indeed, to achieve an ergodic capacity of 1 bps/Hz, approximately 3.91, 3.87, 3.82, and 3.64 dB power saving gains are achieved with the active RIS compared to the passive RIS implementation for $R = 4, 8, 16$, and 32, respectively.

Fig. 14 depicts the positive and negative impact of the amplification gain α and thermal noise power σ_r^2 introduced by the active REs on the FU ergodic capacity, respectively. Indeed, to achieve an ergodic capacity of 1 bps/Hz, approximately 3.85 dB power saving gain is observed as α increases

Fig. 8: OP versus transmit power of FU with $R = 8$, $N_s = 1$ and $\phi = 0$.

Fig. 9: OP versus transmit power of FU with $R = 8$.

from 2 to 4 dB, with $\sigma_r^2 = -50$ dBm. Meanwhile, when σ_r^2 decreases from -15 to -25 and -50 dBm, approximately 9.42 and 17.72 dB respective power saving gains are observed to achieve an ergodic capacity of 0.8 bps/Hz with $\alpha = 2$ dB.

Fig. 15, Fig. 16, and Fig. 17 illustrate the ASER performance versus transmit power for rectangular QAM, cross QAM, and hexagonal QAM schemes, respectively. The asymptotic ASER matches the exact ASER in the high-transmit SNR regimes, thus validating (50), (54), and (58). It is noted that the ASER performance improves with $\{m_{sr}, m_{rf}\}$, amplification gain α , and number of REs R . However, the ASER performance deteriorates with the increase in constellation size M . From Fig. 15, it is noticed that to achieve an ASER of 10^{-2} , approximately 2.87, 3.99, and 6.56 dB power saving gains are observed when $\{m_{sr}, m_{rf}\}$ increases from $\{1, 1\}$ to $\{2, 2\}$, α increases from 2 to 4, and R increases from 8 to 16, respectively, with $M = 8$. From Fig. 16, it is noted that to achieve an ASER of 10^{-1} , approximately 2.08, 4.01, and 6.29 dB power saving gains are obtained when $\{m_{sr}, m_{rf}\}$ increases from $\{1, 1\}$ to $\{2, 2\}$, α increases from 2 to 4, and R increases from 8 to 16, respectively, with $M = 32$. Furthermore, from Fig. 17, it is noticed that to achieve an ASER of 10^{-2} , approximately 3.02, 3.99, and 6.16 dB power saving gains are observed when $\{m_{sr}, m_{rf}\}$ increases from $\{1, 1\}$ to $\{2, 2\}$, α increases from 2 to 4, and R increases from 8 to 16, respectively, with $M = 16$.

Fig. 18 depicts a comparison of the ASER performance among rectangular QAM, cross QAM, and hexagonal QAM schemes. Note that cross QAM consistently delivers a notable performance gain compared to rectangular QAM across all constellation orders. This is attributed to the fact that the cross QAM exhibits lower peak and average powers compared to

Fig. 10: OP versus transmit power of FU with fading mitigation parameter $\{1, 1\}$ and $r_{th} = 1$ bps/Hz.

Fig. 11: OP versus transmit power of FU with $R = 8$ and $r_{th} = 1$ bps/Hz.

rectangular QAM, owing to its more compact design. Furthermore, the hexagonal QAM demonstrates a substantial gain over the cross QAM, standing as the optimum constellation.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper investigated the performance of an active RIS-assisted downlink NOMA network with transceiver hardware impairments and ipSIC. The TAS technique was employed at the BS to achieve transmit diversity gain. Closed-form expressions of OP, ergodic capacity, and asymptotic ergodic capacity were derived in terms of the Meijer-G function for both the NU and the FU. The diversity order of both the NU and the FU was obtained from the asymptotic OP at high SNR. We showed that the diversity order of the NU depend on the fading mitigation parameter of the BS-NU link and the number of transmit antennas at the BS; while the diversity order of the FU depends on the number of REs, number of transmit antennas at the BS, and fading mitigation parameters of the BS-active RIS and active RIS-FU links. For the general-order rectangular QAM, cross QAM, and hexagonal QAM schemes, closed-form ASER asymptotic ASER expressions were derived by using the GCQ approximation method. We showed the superiority of NOMA over OMA in terms of OP, and the outstanding performance of the considered active RIS implementation over a passive RIS-assisted system. Numerical results also evinced that the system performance improves with the amplification gain, number of REs, number of transmit antennas, and with better fading statistics, while the thermal noise introduced by the active REs, ipSIC, and hardware impairments have a significant degenerative impact. From the obtained ASER results, it can be concluded that, for an

Fig. 12: Ergodic capacity versus transmit power of FU with $R = 4$ and $\alpha = 2$ dB.

Fig. 13: Ergodic capacity versus transmit power of FU with fading mitigation parameter $\{2, 2\}$.

equivalent constellation size, the hexagonal QAM exhibits superior performance compared to rectangular QAM and cross QAM schemes.

The potential challenges in implementing an active RIS-assisted NOMA network include RIS reconfiguration for controllable reflection, optimizing RIS deployment and size, and channel estimation, can be thoroughly investigated in the future. Furthermore, the performance of the considered network with multiple downlink users can be a possible future research direction.

APPENDIX A

Let RV X_j be defined as $X_j \triangleq |h_{s,n}|^2$. The selected antenna at the BS, denoted by \hat{j} , by employing the TAS technique is given as

$$\hat{j} = \arg \max_{1 \leq j \leq N_s} \{X_j\}. \quad (61)$$

The CDF of $X_{\hat{j}}$ is given as [39]

$$F_{X_{\hat{j}}}(x) = \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(m_{sn})} \Upsilon \left(m_{sn}, \frac{m_{sn}}{\Omega_{sn}} x \right) \right)^{N_s}. \quad (62)$$

On invoking (3) and (4) in (6), the OP of the NU is derived as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}_n &= 1 - \Pr \left[X_{\hat{j}} \geq \frac{\Lambda_{thf}}{\zeta_n (\beta_f - (\beta_n + \phi_s^2 + \phi_n^2) \Lambda_{thf})}, \right. \\ &\quad \left. X_{\hat{j}} \geq \frac{\Lambda_{thn}}{\zeta_n (\beta_n - (\rho\beta_f + \phi_s^2 + \phi_n^2))} \right] \\ &= \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(m_{sn})} \Upsilon \left(m_{sn}, \frac{m_{sn}\Xi}{\Omega_{sn}\zeta_n} \right) \right)^{N_s}. \end{aligned} \quad (63)$$

Fig. 14: Ergodic capacity versus transmit power of FU with fading mitigation parameters $\{1, 1\}$ and $N_s = 1$.

Fig. 15: ASER versus transmit power of FU for a rectangular QAM with $R = 8$, $N_s = 1$ and $\phi = 0$.

By using [38, eq. (8.352.6)] and representing $e^{-cx} = G_{0,1}^{1,0}[cx|_0]$ in (63), we obtain (7). Further, by employing a high SNR approximation $\Upsilon(a, y) \approx (\frac{y^a}{a})$ in (63), the closed-form expression of the asymptotic OP is obtained as given in (8).

APPENDIX B

Let $Y_j \triangleq \left(\sum_{r=1}^R |h_{s_j r}| |h_{rf}| \right)^2$ in case of an optimal phase shift (i.e., $\text{ang}(\theta_r) = -\text{ang}(h_{s_j r}) - \text{ang}(h_{rf})$), where $\text{ang}(\cdot)$ outputs the angle of the input. An optimal phase shift at the RIS (i.e., a coherent phase shifting design complementing the phase shifts of the RIS channels) for the simplicity of analysis. By employing the TAS technique, the selected antenna at the BS is given as

$$\hat{j} = \arg \max_{1 \leq j \leq N_s} \{Y_j\}. \quad (64)$$

By using the moment-matching method, the CDF of $Y_{\hat{j}}$ is given as

$$F_{Y_{\hat{j}}}(y) = \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\mu)} \Upsilon \left(\mu, \frac{\sqrt{y}}{\Delta} \right) \right)^{N_s}. \quad (65)$$

Further, consider $Z \triangleq \left(\sum_{r=1}^R |h_{rf}| \right)^2$ for an optimal phase shift [50]. The PDF of Z is given as

$$f_Z(z) = \left(\frac{m_{rf}}{\Omega_{rf}} \right)^{m_{rf} R} \frac{1}{\Gamma(m_{rf} R)} z^{m_{rf} R - 1} e^{-\frac{m_{rf}}{\Omega_{rf}} z}. \quad (66)$$

The term \mathcal{I}_1 present in (33) can be expressed as

$$\mathcal{I}_1 = \Pr \left[Y < \frac{\lambda \Lambda_{\text{thf}} Z}{\alpha^2 \beta_f \zeta_f} \right] = \int_0^\infty f_Z(z) F_Y \left(\frac{\lambda \Lambda_{\text{thf}} z}{\alpha^2 \beta_f \zeta_f} \right) dz. \quad (67)$$

Fig. 16: ASER versus transmit power of FU for a cross QAM with $N_s = 1$ and $\phi = 0$.

Fig. 17: ASER versus transmit power of FU for a hexagonal QAM with $N_s = 1$ and $\phi = 0$.

On invoking the corresponding PDF and CDF in (67) and representing $e^{-\sqrt{cz}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} G_{0,2}^{2,0} \left[\frac{cz}{4} \middle| 0, \frac{1}{2} \right]$ [49, eq. (01.03.26.0008.01)], and by using [49, eq. (07.33.21.0088.01)], we obtain (35). Further, by using a high SNR approximation $\Upsilon(a, y) \approx (\frac{y^a}{a})$ in (67) and using [38, eq. (3.381.4)], we obtain (36).

APPENDIX C

From (33), the term \mathcal{I}_2 can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{I}_2 &= \Pr \left[Y < \frac{\Lambda_{\text{thf}}}{\alpha^2 \beta_f \zeta_f} \right] = F_Y \left(\frac{\Lambda_{\text{thf}}}{\alpha^2 \beta_f \zeta_f} \right) \\ &= \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\mu)} \Upsilon \left(\mu, \frac{1}{\Delta} \sqrt{\frac{\Lambda_{\text{thf}}}{\alpha^2 \beta_f \zeta_f}} \right) \right)^{N_s}. \end{aligned} \quad (68)$$

By using [38, eq. (8.352.6)] and [49, eq. (01.03.26.0008.01)], we obtain (39). Further, by using a high SNR approximation $\Upsilon(a, y) \approx (\frac{y^a}{a})$ in (68), we obtain (40).

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Fig. 18: Comparison among various QAM schemes with $N_s = 1$ and $\phi = 0$.

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